

PRISM

POLICY, REFORM, & INNOVATION IN SOCIAL MEDICINE

Volume 1: Issue 2 (September 2024)

SCHOOL OF
MEDICINE

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Perceptions of Workplace Violence by US Medical Students – Starting the Conversation

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Abstract

Background: Workplace violence (WPV) against healthcare workers is a longstanding issue, yet insufficient data exists on WPV experienced by medical students during clinical training. While studies have been performed on the subject in other countries including Vietnam, Iran, Singapore, Israel, Malaysia, Australia, and China, there are gaps in the literature regarding institutions in the United States (US). The Association of American Medical Colleges (AAMC) gathers survey data including workplace violence from graduating US medical students, although aggregate data has not been published. This multi-institutional, mixed methods study aims to quantify WPV encountered by medical students, describe experiences via qualitative interviews, and identify primary sources of WPV to facilitate systematic improvements.

Methods: An anonymous survey was distributed to medical students engaged in clinical training at participating United States medical schools. Details about WPV experiences, using multiple-choice questions, drop-down boxes, and free text responses were collected. Data was extracted from RedCap and analyzed using Excel. Double blind interviews were conducted with volunteer participants.

Results: The study included 128 participants, primarily third-year students (50%). 66.4% of students reported no experiences with WPV. The most reported type of WPV was sexual innuendo (41.4%), followed by verbal abuse (32.9%), threats (17.1%), and violence (8.6%). Surgery was perceived as the specialty most likely to experience WPV, while Family Medicine was seen as the least likely. Qualitative interview data provided insight into anecdotal stories experienced by students.

Conclusion: This preliminary data underscores the need to address WPV to enhance student learning and patient care. This study provides foundational insights necessary for addressing WPV in medical education and improving the clinical training environment. Future stages of this study aim to deepen understanding and inform broader, systemic interventions.

Introduction

Current literature demonstrates that workplace violence (WPV) against healthcare workers is a persistent issue faced by practicing providers[1,2]. According to the Bureau of Labor Statistics, healthcare and social assistance workers accounted for approximately 73% of all nonfatal workplace injuries and illnesses due to violence in 2018[2]. The World Health Organization estimates suggest that between 8% and 38% of health workers experience physical violence at some point in their careers, with many more exposed to verbal aggression[1]. WPV has been noted to be highest in Asian and North American countries, with most workers having exposure to some form of violence (61.9%)[3]. In this same study, non-physical violence was more common than physical violence (42.5% and 24.4%, respectively). Of the forms of non-physical violence experienced by licensed providers, verbal abuse was the most common (57.6%) followed by threats (33.2%) and sexual harassment (12.4%)[4].

While much attention has been given to WPV experienced by healthcare professionals, there is a notable paucity of data specifically examining WPV experienced by medical students, particularly in the United States. While studies have been performed on the subject in Vietnam, Iran, Singapore, Israel, Malaysia, Australia, and China, literature on this topic for medical students in the United States is lacking. This is a clear oversight, as medical students in clinical training are placed in a position that subjects them to the same incidents as other healthcare providers – and in some cases, students are notably more vulnerable.

Medical students are exposed to many patients, residents, attendings, and hospital staff during their clinical year, often with little experience. One global study concerning WPV against nursing and medical students has shown that more than half of medical students report experiencing verbal violence during their clinical rotations[4]. In a 2019 study, it was found that 64% of medical students reported at least one incident of mistreatment by faculty members while 75.5% reported mistreatment from residents. This study also found a correlation between the mistreatment during training and burnout[5]. Furthermore, 14.6% of students have considered leaving the profession due to WPV experiences, and 27.8% report that these incidents have affected patient care[4]. In another study on WPV against medical students in Vietnam, 29.3% of respondents had experienced verbal abuse during clinical training[6]. Similar results were reported in a study on WPV against medical students in Iran, where 63% of respondents reported verbal abuse, followed by physical (25.7%) and racial (23.0%)[6]. In both studies, most students did not report the incidents[6,7].

The Association of American Medical Colleges (AAMC) collects survey data from graduating medical students each year, which highlights perceived incidences of violence across various specialties, including Surgery, Obstetrics and Gynecology, and Internal Medicine. Rates of public embarrassment have been high over the past four years, from 2019-2023 (38.1% - 40.4%)[7]. Of those who experienced public embarrassment, most students cited clerkship faculty in the clinical setting as the main driver of the embarrassment when compared to pre-clerkship faculty, residents/interns, nurses, administrators, or other students[7]. Aggregate data on these experiences has not been publicly published.

These staggering global numbers warrant a call for action to address WPV against medical students. It is widely accepted that medical training is a stressful time for students and their loved ones. Nearly a third of medical students experience clinical depression during their training with a large portion of students experiencing burnout[9]. The learning and work environment, along with worries about the future, were among the leading causes of burnout rather than the individual's attributes[9,10]. As we continue to assess ways to improve the medical field and training, it is imperative that student experiences are valued.

To implement effective and systemic improvements in the United States, it is essential to identify the perpetrators and types of WPV that medical students encounter. This study, which is part of a multi-institutional initiative, seeks to quantitatively assess the prevalence and types of WPV experienced

by medical students. Additionally, it is designed to better understand the qualitative aspects of these experiences and ways to improve them through in-depth qualitative interviews. Through its quantitative and qualitative measures, the study aims to uncover patterns and provide a foundation for developing targeted interventions to enhance the safety and well-being of medical trainees. This effort is crucial for ensuring that medical students can complete their education in a safe and supportive environment, contributing to better patient care and a more robust healthcare system. By integrating survey data with in-depth double-blind interviews, the study aims to capture both the breadth and depth of WPV encounters, providing a more nuanced understanding of this issue. Here, we discuss preliminary data from this multi-institutional study, focusing on qualitative data.

Methods

This study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining both quantitative and qualitative measures to comprehensively assess medical students' experiences with workplace violence (WPV) during clinical training. Due to the sensitive content of this study, participating institutions will remain anonymous as the overarching goal of this manuscript is to incite positive change. WPV against medical students is a global issue, not specific to the participating institutions.

Quantitative

This IRB-approved study initially involved an anonymous survey aimed at understanding medical students' perceptions and experiences of workplace violence during clinical training. The survey was hosted on RedCap, a secure web-based application designed for data collection in research studies, and distributed electronically to medical students across multiple institutions via institutional email lists. The survey included a mix of standardized multiple-choice questions, drop-down menus, and open-ended free-text responses to gather data surrounding perceptions of safety by students in settings involving patients, residents, attendings, and their peers. Demographic information such as age, gender, year of study, and specialty interests was also collected to facilitate detailed analysis. Anonymity was maintained throughout the survey process to encourage honest and accurate reporting of WPV experiences.

Qualitative

The final question of the survey included the option to opt-in for a follow-up blinded qualitative interview. Those who opted in provided contact information while their survey responses remained anonymous and were assigned a unique study number before proceeding to part two of the study. These students were contacted by approved study personnel from their own institution to confirm participation and schedule the interview. To further ensure confidentiality and minimize bias, the interviews were conducted by approved study personnel from different institutions.

Interviews were scheduled via secure encrypted email using the blind carbon copy (BCC) feature so that neither the interviewer nor the interviewee knew the name of the other. The interviews were conducted via a secure online video chat platform, WebEx, to accommodate participants from various geographic locations. During these sessions, interviewers and interviewees were only allowed to use first names, or a pseudonym, to maintain a level of anonymity and reduce potential biases.

Interviews were recorded with the participants' verbal consent and transcribed using the video chat platform's encrypted artificial intelligence (AI) transcription service. The initial transcriptions were then reviewed and cross-checked by the anonymous interviewer for accuracy.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data from the surveys were exported from RedCap into Excel for analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic data and the prevalence of distinct types of WPV. Frequencies and percentages were calculated for categorical variables, while means and standard deviations were computed for continuous variables. Qualitative data from the interview transcripts were analyzed using thematic analysis. The transcriptions were coded manually by researchers at the home

institutions, who identified common themes and patterns related to WPV experiences. These themes were then compared across different institutions to identify any pervasive issues or unique challenges faced by medical students in various clinical environments.

This study was approved by the Institutional Review Boards (IRBs) of all participating institutions. An information form was sent with the initial survey invitation and participation supplied implied consent. Informed consent was obtained verbally at the start of each interview. Measures were taken to ensure the confidentiality and anonymity of all participants throughout the study. Data security protocols were strictly adhered to, with all electronic data stored on encrypted, password-protected servers accessible only to authorized research personnel.

Results

The study included 128 participants, primarily third-year students (50%) (Table 1). 66.4% of students reported no experiences with WPV. The most reported type of WPV was sexual innuendo (41.4%), followed by verbal abuse (32.9%), threats (17.1%), and physical violence (8.6%) (Figure 1). Surgery was perceived as the specialty most likely to experience WPV, while family medicine was seen as the least likely (Figure 2).

Analysis of qualitative interviews exposed themes including gender differences, physical safety/built environment, verbal/emotional violence, training/preparedness, cultural environment, and support systems. While some participants focused more on physical safety and the built environment, others shared experiences of verbal mistreatment and psychological violence from both patients and members of the healthcare team. Furthermore, most participants noted the importance of a safe environment and culture during training. All participants touched on a lack of training and preparedness they felt while navigating violence in clinical settings. Here, we include many of these pervasive themes.

Table 1: Demographic data of study participants

Demographic		Number of Respondents (n)
Gender	Male	46
	Female	78
	Nonbinary	3
	Transgender	1
Race	Caucasian	92
	Black/African American	10
	Asian	12
	Other, unspecified	13
Year of Medical School Training	MS1	14
	MS2	10
	MS3	64
	MS4	40

Figure 1: Categories of workplace violence reported, stratified by gender.

Figure 2: Participants' subjective interpretation of which specialties students are most (orange) and least (blue) likely to experience workplace violence.

Physical safety/environment

When inquired about their perception of safety in clinical settings, many participants mentioned their physical safety and reflected on different environments. For example, environments such as the emergency or psychiatry departments were cited as sites of increased perceived risk for physical and verbal violence.

In these settings, security is often present to de-escalate violence. One participant recounted, “...We had a [young] patient having some psychiatric problems...being loud and a little bit violent towards nursing. Security was called and I think we had like, five or six people there to help contain the patient...the [attendings] were trying to use verbal reassurance to calm the patient, but having security there makes me

feel a lot safer.” The sentiment of a physical intervention providing a feeling of safety for students was echoed in several interviews.

Verbal/emotional violence

Participants also detailed instances of verbal/emotional violence that made them feel unsafe during their clinical training. These experiences were often linked to the perceived cultural environment, or the reputation, of a particular specialty. One student recollected an interaction with a scrub nurse on a surgical rotation, “... every single thing I had done that morning... was wrong, I had touched something, or I did this, or I had done that. And it just kept involving [them] screaming across the room at me when I was just trying to get gloves or ... or like anything really. [They weren't] targeting anybody else in the room. It was only me. I was the only student there...and not one attending or resident stepped in ... it was in front of the whole OR...But I think that was just a very particular instance of being very taken advantage of as a med student and treated like a not normal human being...” Unfortunately, stories of humiliation were not isolated to this interview. Furthermore, the sentiment of a culture that is fundamentally inhospitable to speaking out against mistreatment was a theme throughout the interviews.

Cultural environment

It became clear through the interviews that cultural environment is a significant factor, impacting not only safety, but patient care, education, and the decision to pursue one specialty over another. The culture of an environment influences safety and the ability to learn and care for patients. One student described the positive impact of the culture during the family medicine clerkship, “I always felt safe in family medicine...I felt like I had room to be a student and a learner and be wrong and feel safe [while] being wrong....When I was right, I was able to drive the bus and be right and [was] celebrated. I felt like that was the culture of [our] family medicine department and I remember really feeling like I learned a lot and thrived because I was able to be a learner.” As a result of a safe culture, this individual was afforded the space to learn and was able to become a leader and further grow as a future physician. This quote was similar to the feelings of others and provides a glimpse into the qualitative context for the qualitative trends found in the survey portion.

Discussion

The findings of this study underscore the significant and multifaceted issue of workplace violence against medical students during clinical training. The results reveal a concerning prevalence of both physical and non-physical violence, with verbal abuse reported most often. This aligns with existing literature on WPV against healthcare workers, where verbal aggression frequently surpasses physical violence in terms of occurrence[1]. The exposure of medical students to such hostile environments not only jeopardizes their immediate well-being but also has broader implications for their professional development and the overall quality of patient care.

The quantitative data in the present study highlights a large number of students who have experienced workplace violence. Among those who reported WPV, sexual innuendo was the most common form, affecting 41.4% of respondents, followed by verbal abuse (32.9%), threats (17.1%), and physical violence (8.6%). This distribution suggests that non-physical forms of WPV, particularly those with sexual overtones, are pervasive and perhaps under-addressed within the clinical training environment. This result is striking, as sexual harassment was much less reported in other similar studies at only 12.4%, 6.4% and 3%[3,7,8]. However, one study on sexual harassment conducted across four U.S. medical schools revealed that 36.6% reported sexual harassment by a faculty or staff member, 38.5% by a fellow student, and incidents were significantly higher for women and multiracial students[12]. Furthermore, these students were more likely to report academic disengagement and PTSD[12]. Although anecdotally common, sexual harassment against medical students has not been widely discussed in the literature and requires further attention and investigation.

Qualitative interviews provide a deeper understanding of the contexts and impacts of these

violent encounters. Many students reported feeling unsafe in specific clinical settings, such as emergency and psychiatry departments, where the likelihood of encountering aggressive behavior from patients is higher. This may potentially be due to the lack of inhibition prevalent in such patients, whether from substance use or disease process. The theme of safety in clinical settings such as the ED and psychiatry department has been reported in prior studies and seems to be a common location susceptible to WPV[3,7]. According to the AAMC, nearly 50% of ED physicians say they have been assaulted, and 70% of ED nurses report being kicked or hit on the job[12].

The presence of security personnel was frequently mentioned as a critical factor in enhancing students' sense of safety. This finding suggests that institutional measures to increase security presence, rapid response mechanisms, or providing methods for students to safely request security during perceived moments of lack of safety, without judgment or repercussion, could be beneficial.

A significant gap identified in this study is the inadequacy of current training programs in preparing medical students to handle WPV. Many students criticized the existing safety training as ineffective, particularly those that relied on scare tactics without providing practical de-escalation techniques. This highlights the need for more comprehensive training programs that equip students with the skills to recognize early signs of potential violence and employ effective de-escalation strategies. Ensuring that such training is embedded within the medical curriculum could enhance students' confidence and competence in managing WPV. A study on simulation training for nurses to combat WPV revealed that the training course intervention with role-playing improved nursing staff's self-perception and confidence in handling WPV[12]. Another study on the implementation of a case-based safety workshop for medical students yielded similar results and improved knowledge and attitudes by 53% over the previous safety curriculum[14]. Similar role play and case-based training should be considered and trialed in medical student education before the start of clerkships in medical schools nationwide.

The cultural environment within clinical settings emerged as a crucial factor influencing students' experiences of WPV. Positive cultural environments, such as those observed in family medicine departments, where students felt safe, supported, and valued, contrasted sharply with the toxic cultures reported in some surgical and high-stress specialties. These findings were consistent across quantitative and qualitative data collection. They emphasize the importance of fostering a supportive and inclusive culture within all clinical departments to mitigate the occurrence of WPV and enhance the educational experience of medical students. Conversely, instances of humiliation or bullying by senior providers yield emotional and psychological tolls on students. Unfortunately, the hostile cultural environment in certain specialties seems to foster a climate where mistreatment is normalized, discouraging students from speaking out against it. These findings are echoed by the 2023 AAMC annual survey for graduating medical students, which demonstrated that of reported instances of WPV, 54.3% occurred during the surgery clerkship, followed by OBGYN (31.0%) and internal medicine (21.4%)[7]. Psychiatry (6.3%), neurology (7.4%), and family medicine clerkships (8.2%) had the lowest percentages of all reported WPV, according to the survey[7].

The results of this study call for action to address WPV against medical students. Institutions must implement policies that promote a zero-tolerance approach to all forms of WPV, ensuring that incidents are promptly reported and addressed. Additionally, creating support systems, such as counseling services and peer support groups, can provide affected students with the necessary resources to cope with their experiences.

Many students throughout interviews noted a lack of access to methods for reporting incidents. Even more students reported that they refrained from reporting misconduct due to fear of their anonymity being exposed, repercussions, or simply not wanting to have to discuss unfortunate situations further with school administration, which are common sentiments among medical students[7].

A notable takeaway from our interviews were the ideas students have for implementing changes

that would increase their perception of safety. This emphasizes the importance for institutions to engage students in these discussions in a safe, non-retaliatory, non-punitive setting, such as focus groups or town hall meetings.

Of note, most of the prior studies referenced have been conducted in countries outside of the United States. The present study aims to highlight WPV against medical students at different institutions throughout the United States, initiating a nationwide conversation. Although WPV against medical students is a worldwide issue, future studies should continue to explore this topic throughout the United States, as each country has a unique medical education system with nuance and differences in overall medical student training experience.

Several limitations could have influenced the data. Participation in the survey and follow-up interviews was voluntary, potentially leading to a bias where those with particularly negative or positive experiences were more likely to respond. This self-selection bias might skew the data towards more extreme experiences of WPV, either overstating or understating the true prevalence. Continued work related to this topic can help mitigate such discrepancies.

Conclusion

As the healthcare landscape continues to evolve, particularly considering challenges such as the COVID-19 pandemic, which has seen significant increases in aggression and WPV across many clinical settings, it is imperative that we better understand and address the specific experiences and needs of medical students facing workplace violence. This research aims to contribute to that understanding and inform strategies to create safer learning and working environments for the next generation of healthcare professionals. Moving forward, the next steps involve expanding this research as part of a larger multi-institutional study to capture a more comprehensive and representative picture of WPV across different regions and institutions. Cohort studies may provide insight into the potential long-term effects of such treatment. Comparative analysis by region could uncover unique challenges and effective strategies tailored to specific geographical contexts. Furthermore, longitudinal studies are needed to understand the long-term effects of WPV on medical students' career choices, mental health, and patient care practices. Institutions must prioritize creating safer, more supportive environments for medical trainees. This includes implementing robust zero-tolerance policies against all forms of WPV, enhancing practical safety training programs, and fostering a culture that values and protects students' well-being. Providing accessible, non-punitive reporting mechanisms and engaging students in safety discussions are crucial steps towards mitigating WPV and ensuring a healthier, more conducive learning environment for future healthcare professionals. By addressing these issues, we can work towards a more resilient and empathetic healthcare system, ultimately benefiting both providers and patients.

References

1. Lim MC, Jeffree MS, Saupin SS, Giloi N, Lukman KA. Workplace violence in healthcare settings: The risk factors, implications and collaborative preventive measures. *Ann Med Surg (Lond)*. 2022;78:103727. Published 2022 May 13. doi:10.1016/j.amsu.2022.103727
2. U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics. The Census of Fatal Occupational Injuries. 2023 Survey of Occupational Injuries and Illnesses. 2022. Employer-reported Workplace injuries and illnesses 2023
3. Liu J, Gan Y, Jiang H, et al. Prevalence of workplace violence against healthcare workers: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Occup Environ Med*. 2019;76(12):927- 937. doi:10.1136/oemed-2019-105849
4. Warshawski S. Workplace violence directed at nursing and medical students - What can students tell us about it?. *J Prof Nurs*. 2021;37(6):1110-1118. doi:10.1016/j.profnurs.2021.09.004
5. Cook AF, Arora VM, Rasinski KA, Curlin FA, Yoon JD. The prevalence of medical student mistreatment and its association with burnout. *Acad Med*. 2014;89(5):749-754. doi:10.1097/ACM.0000000000000204
6. Vu LG, Nguyen Hoang L, Le Vu Ngoc M, et al. Professional Preparedness Implications of Workplace Violence against Medical Students in Hospitals: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Inquiry*. 2023;60:469580231179894. doi:10.1177/00469580231179894
7. Sadeghi S, Shadman A, Mardi A, Hackett D. Reactions and perspectives of medical students on workplace violence during clinical training in Ardabil, Iran, 2020. *BMC Med Educ*. 2023;23(1):435. Published 2023 Jun 13. doi:10.1186/s12909-023-04426-7
8. Association of American Medical Colleges. Medical School Graduation Questionnaire. July 2023. <https://www.aamc.org/media/68936/download>
9. Puthran R, Zhang MW, Tam WW, Ho RC. Prevalence of depression among medical students: a meta-analysis. *Med Educ*. 2016;50(4):456-468. doi:10.1111/medu.12962
10. Dyrbye L, Shanafelt T. A narrative review on burnout experienced by medical students and residents. *Med Educ*. 2016;50(1):132-149. doi:10.1111/medu.12927
11. McClain T, Kammer-Kerwick M, Wood L, Temple JR, Busch-Armendariz N. Sexual Harassment Among Medical Students: Prevalence, Prediction, and Correlated Outcomes. *Workplace Health Saf*. 2021;69(6):257-267. doi:10.1177/2165079920969402
12. Budd K. Rising violence in the emergency department. AAMC. <https://www.aamc.org/news/rising-violence-emergency-department>. Published February 24, 2020. Accessed August 13, 2024.
13. Ming JL, Huang HM, Hung SP, et al. Using Simulation Training to Promote Nurses' Effective Handling of Workplace Violence: A Quasi-Experimental Study. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2019;16(19):3648. Published 2019 Sep 28. doi:10.3390/ijerph16193648
14. Strowd LC, Grant E, Peacock B, Callahan K. Safety in Numbers: Successful Student-Approved Case-Based Interprofessional Safety Workshop Utilizing Simulated Real-Life Safety Cases. *MedEdPORTAL*. 2020;16:10874. Published 2020 Jan 31. doi:10.15766/mep_2374-8265.10874

Impact of Pre-Clinical Teaching on Medical Students' Attitudes & Interest in Nephrology

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Abstract

Background: Teaching during the medical students' clinical years is critical to deciding what specialty they pursue. Previous research in nephrology and other fields (e.g. psychiatry, general surgery) has explored the impact of clinical rotations on medical students' attitudes towards and preference for that specialty as a future career, but little work has been done to explore the impact of pre-clinical education. We present the impact of the Renal Block (4-week pre-clinical nephrology curriculum for first-year medical students) on students' attitudes towards and desires to pursue nephrology as a specialty.

Methods: We administered surveys to first-year medical students at the University of North Carolina (UNC) and Columbia University (CU) for the 2022-2023 academic year before and after the Renal Block. Surveys consisted of attitude-based questions that aimed to evaluate students' perceptions and preferences.

Results: UNC and CU pre-survey response rates were 51.5% (100/194) and 21.4% (30/140), respectively. UNC post-survey response rate was 40.2% (78/194) and no post-survey responses were collected from CU. There were statistically significant differences (p -value < 0.05) between UNC pre- and post-surveys showing improved attitudes towards nephrology and increased interest in the field. Work-life balance, intellectual curiosity, and long-term patient relationships were the top three factors affecting choice of specialty amongst medical students.

Conclusions: The Renal Block had a positive impact on first-year medical students' attitudes towards and interest in pursuing nephrology as a career. Furthermore, students consistently ranked work-life balance as an extremely important factor when choosing a specialty.

Introduction

In recent years, interest in nephrology has decreased, as reflected by a reduction in the number of candidates applying for the field.[1-2] A variety of efforts have been conducted to try and increase interest in nephrology.[3] Previous research in nephrology and other fields (e.g. family medicine, psychiatry, general surgery) has explored the impact of clinical rotations on medical students' attitudes towards and preference for that specialty as a future career. In most studies, the impact on self-reported attitudes to a given specialty post-clinical rotation was positive.[4-6] Additionally, the studies in family medicine and general surgery saw improvement in specialty-specific knowledge (e.g. diagnosis/management of acute and chronic concerns) and skills (e.g. communication skills) post-clerkship.[4,6] Regarding the impact on interest in pursuing a given specialty as a career, the study in general surgery saw an increase in ranking preference from the 10th to the 5th position compared to other specialties post-clerkship.[6] Similarly, the study in psychiatry found students reporting the highest preference level for this specialty as a career choice following completion of the clerkship, with a notable decline in preference one year later.[5]

The learning that occurs during the clinical years of a medical student's education is critical to deciding what specialty they pursue.[7] However, very little research has been done to evaluate the impact of education in the pre-clinical years on a medical student's specialty preference. In fact, this has not been explored in the field of nephrology. Thus, this study aims to explore the impact of the Renal Block (4-week pre-clinical nephrology curriculum for first-year medical students) on students' attitudes towards nephrology and their desires to pursue nephrology as a specialty.

The novelty of this study and the present need to boost interest in specialties with declining interest make this study especially important. It can shed insight on the value of the pre-clinical years in shaping a medical student's decision to choose a specialty and the efficacy of this approach in sparking interest in a given subject/field. We hypothesize that medical students' attitudes towards nephrology will improve and that the number of medical students interested in nephrology will increase post-Renal Block.

Methods

A 12-question pre-survey and a 15-question post-survey were administered to the first-year medical students enrolled at the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill School of Medicine (n=194) and Columbia University Vagelos College of Physicians and Surgeons (n=140) during the 2022-2023 academic year using an anonymized Qualtrics survey. The pre-survey consisted of attitude-based questions that aimed to evaluate medical students' perceptions about nephrology and their preferences when choosing a specialty prior to the Renal Block. The post-survey was identical to the pre-survey, with additional questions to assess if the Renal Block had any influence on students' opinions. Once collected, R (version 4.3.2) was employed to conduct a Wilcoxon rank sum test on survey responses for comparing different surveys. The outcomes were then graphically represented using the 'ggplot2' package within R.'

Results

UNC pre-survey response rate was 51.5% (100/194) and CU pre-survey response rate was 21.4% 30/140. UNC post-survey response rate was 40.2% (78/194) and no post-survey responses were collected from CU due to technical issues. Not all questions were answered by every student.

At a p-value significance level of 0.05, there were statistically significant differences between UNC pre- and post-surveys showing an increase in agreement with several statements regarding attitudes towards and interest in nephrology (Figures 1-2).

The Renal Block had an integral influence on these attitudes (Figure 3). Work-life balance,

intellectual curiosity, and long-term patient relationships were the top three factors affecting choice of specialty amongst medical students (Table 1).

Figure 1: Distribution of students' answers to statements on Attitudes to Nephrology surveys (Part I)

Nephrology is a highly intellectual specialty where an individual heavily incorporates critical thinking and problem-solving skills.

An individual's future success as a nephrologist is directly correlated with their skills in mathematics.

Nephrology is too complex.

I am confident in my knowledge of nephrology.

There is a high demand for nephrologists.

X-axis ranges from -1 to 1, with 0 representing a neutral response (“Neither Agree nor Disagree”). Skewed extension of the bars on either side of the origin indicates that a greater proportion of respondents were in agreement (more negative values) or disagreement (more positive values) with the statement.

CU_Pre = Columbia University Pre-Survey
 UNC_Pre = University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill Pre-Survey
 UNC_Post = University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill Post-Survey

Figure 2: Distribution of students’ answers to statements on Attitudes to Nephrology surveys (Part II)

I find the field of nephrology interesting.

I could see myself as a nephrologist in the future.

I understand what a nephrologist does.

I am aware of the different specializations within nephrology.

I am interested in a nephrology rotation during the clinical years.

X-axis ranges from -1 to 1, with 0 representing a neutral response (“Neither Agree nor Disagree”). Skewed extension of the bars on either side of the origin indicates that a greater proportion of respondents were in agreement (more negative values) or disagreement (more positive values) with the statement.

CU_Pre = Columbia University Pre-Survey
 UNC_Pre = University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill Pre-Survey
 UNC_Post = University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill Post-Survey

Figure 3: Distribution of students’ answers to statements regarding impact of Renal Block (post-survey only)

Table 1: Ranking of Important Factors to Medical Students when Selecting Specialty

	CU Pre-Survey	UNC Pre-Survey	UNC Post-Survey
Factors Affecting Choice of Specialty	Number of times listed amongst top 3 factors	Number of times listed amongst top 3 factors	Number of times listed amongst top 3 factors
<i>Overnight Call</i>	0% (0/30)	17.33% (13/75)	11.11% (7/63)
<i>Weekend Call/Off</i>	6.67% (2/30)	22.67% (17/75)	23.81% (15/63)
<i>Salary</i>	20% (6/30)	18.67% (14/75)	19.05% (12/63)
<i>Work-Life Balance</i>	70% (21/30)	81.33% (61/75)	85.71% (54/63)
<i>Intellectual Curiosity</i>	90% (27/30)	54.67% (41/75)	60.32% (38/63)
<i>Long-Term Relationship w/ Patients</i>	43.33% (13/30)	46.67% (35/75)	47.62% (30/63)
<i>Procedures</i>	26.67% (8/30)	28% (21/75)	23.81% (15/63)
<i>Personal/Life Experiences</i>	43.33% (13/30)	28% (21/75)	26.98% (17/63)
<i>Other</i>	0% (0/30)	2.67% (2/75)	1.59% (1/63)

CU = Columbia University

UNC = University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Discussion

Education in the pre-clinical years serves as the foundation for medical students' journey to becoming caring and competent physicians. However, in recent years, the amount of time dedicated to education in the pre-clinical years has decreased at many institutions. [8] Additionally, many educators have noted reduced facetime with students and observed declining interest in various specialties. Our paper shows the importance of pre-clinical education in affecting the attitudes and future specialty interests of medical students by exploring the impact of the pre-clinical Renal curriculum on medical students' attitudes towards nephrology.

As shown in Figure 1, medical students reported increased confidence in their knowledge of nephrology and decreased association of over-complexity with nephrology post-Renal Block. These statistically significant results suggest that the Renal Block was efficacious in making nephrology more accessible as a subject. While these findings may be partially attributed to the fact that most medical students have not encountered renal physiology in any of their coursework prior to medical school, they highlight the value of quality education in these foundational years on a student's experience with a subject and exposure to a given specialty.

A positive learning experience with a given subject can subsequently impact medical students' views of the associated specialty and their likelihood of considering the specialty as a future career. As shown in Figure 2, medical students reported increased desire to pursue a clinical rotation in nephrology and greater interest in nephrology as a specialty post-Renal Block. As seen in Figure 3, many students also felt that the Renal Block itself had a notable impact on their attitudes towards and interest in the field. These results exemplify the power of education in the pre-clinical years in boosting medical students' interest in a given specialty/career. Most students enter medical school undecided in terms of specialty choice and are unaware of the breadth of opportunities available to them. Clinical rotations are integral to a student's process of determining their future specialty; however, the guidance and exposure that can be offered to medical students during pre-clinical teaching are essential to introducing students to their options for fourth-year rotations and promoting interest in specialties early-on.

While academic interest in a specialty is fundamental, there are a variety of other factors that medical students consider when ultimately selecting their future specialty. Our survey asked medical students to rank the following factors from most to least important: overnight call, weekend call/off, salary, work-life balance, intellectual curiosity, long-term relationships with patients, procedures, personal/life experiences, and other. Of these factors, the majority of medical students at both UNC and CU ranked "Work-Life Balance," "Intellectual Curiosity," and "Long-Term Relationships with Patients" among their top three (Table 1). For the medical students at UNC, these rankings remained consistent even after the Renal Block. Given that the above factors play a significant role in shaping students' perceptions of specialties, it is essential to evaluate and address these to promote interest in specialties. During the Renal Block at UNC, students experienced "A Day in the Life of a Nephrologist," an informational session for students to learn more about this career and individual journeys from a panel of nephrologists. We wondered if this intervention would alter the composition of the top three factors post-Renal Block but hypothesized that "Work-Life Balance" would be one of the top three factors across both pre- and post-surveys. With rising rates of physician burnout and suicide, work-life harmony has become an increasingly important value in medicine over the years.[9] The results of this study are consistent with this changing trend and signify that work-life harmony needs to be a priority if we want to attract more students to specialties in need.

In summary, this study shows that pre-clinical education can have a powerful impact on medical students' attitudes towards and interest in a given specialty and highlights that work-life balance is one of the most important factors to medical students when choosing a specialty as their career. While these results were acquired in the context of nephrology, the implications are applicable to all other specialties in medicine. These findings exemplify the potential of education in the pre-clinical years to influence medical students' interest in a given subject/specialty and their desire to pursue said specialty as a career.

Conclusion

The three key findings from this study were: 1) medical students demonstrated improved attitudes towards nephrology post-Renal Block, reporting more confidence in their knowledge and the accessibility of nephrology; 2) medical students reported increased interest in nephrology post-Renal Block; and 3) medical students ranked work-life balance, intellectual curiosity, and long-term patient relationships highest when selecting a specialty.

By examining the impact of the pre-clinical years on students' attitudes towards and interest in a given specialty, this study begins to address a literature gap in educational research related to nephrology and other specialties. As demonstrated by the above findings in the context of nephrology, exposure in the early stages of medical education can strongly influence students' perspectives and future exploration of specialties. This exposure ideally includes both the foundational knowledge relevant to a particular specialty and a snapshot of what it means to practice in a given specialty. Given that lifestyle factors are an important consideration for students when choosing a career, it is essential for leaders of every field to prioritize advancements in this domain to boost interest in specialties with declining interest.

Subsequent studies can expand on these findings at other institutions across additional specialties and explore what aspects of teaching in the pre-clinical years are most influential on students to improve future medical education curricula. Furthermore, studies on the efficacy of pre-clinical education may be bolstered by exploring the number of students who express interest in a given specialty after the corresponding pre-clinical curriculum that goes on to pursue said specialty at the end of their clinical years.

References

1. Beck, Natalie, et al. "Internal Medicine Residents' Perceptions of Nephrology as a Career: A Focus Group Study." *Kidney360*, vol. 1, no. 10, 19 Aug. 2020, pp. 1052–1059, <https://doi.org/10.34067/KID.0003652020>
2. Hsu, Chi-yuan, et al. "Improving the Nephrology Match." *Journal of the American Society of Nephrology*, vol. 26, no. 11, 4 Sept. 2015, pp. 2634–2639, <https://doi.org/10.1681/asn.2015040420>.
3. Burgner, Anna, et al. "Increasing Interest in Nephrology: Focusing on the Medical Students." *American Journal of Nephrology*, vol. 50, no. 1, 2019, pp. 1–3, <https://doi.org/10.1159/000501060>.
4. Thai, Thuy T. N., et al. "Can a Family Medicine Rotation Improve Medical Students' Knowledge, Skills and Attitude towards Primary Care in Vietnam? A Pre-Test–Post-Test Comparison and Qualitative Survey." *Tropical Medicine & International Health*, vol. 25, no. 2, 13 Nov. 2019, pp. 264–275, <https://doi.org/10.1111/tmi.13326>
5. Hor, Esther Shan Lin, et al. "Changing Attitudes to Psychiatry and Interest in the Specialty as a Career Choice during Clinical Undergraduate Years at a Medical School in Penang, Malaysia." *Irish Journal of Medical Science (1971 -)*, vol. 189, no. 1, 23 July 2019, pp. 253–259, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11845-019-02064-x>
6. Al-Heeti, Khalaf N.M., et al. "The Effect of General Surgery Clerkship Rotation on the Attitude of Medical Students towards General Surgery as a Future Career." *Journal of Surgical Education*, vol. 69, no. 4, July 2012, pp. 544–549, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsurg.2012.04.005>.
7. Weissman, Charles, et al. "Medical Specialty Considerations by Medical Students Early in Their Clinical Experience." *Israel Journal of Health Policy Research*, vol. 1, no. 1, 12 Mar. 2012, <https://doi.org/10.1186/2045-4015-1-13>
8. Murphy, Brendan. "Medical Schools Ponder Move to Shorter Pre-Clerkship Curriculum." *American Medical Association*, 17 Nov. 2021, www.ama-assn.org/medical-students/clinical-rotations/medical-schools-ponder-move-shorter-pre-clerkship-curriculum
9. De Hert, Stefan. "Burnout in Healthcare Workers: Prevalence, Impact and Preventative Strategies." *Local and Regional Anesthesia*, vol. 13, no. 13, 28 Oct. 2020, pp. 171–183, <https://doi.org/10.2147/lra.s240564>.

Oncology in Low- and Middle-Income Countries: The Elimination of Cervical Cancer

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"One woman dies of cervical cancer every two minutes, making it one of the greatest threats to women's health... But it doesn't have to be this way. Cervical cancer is one of the most preventable and treatable forms of cancer." - Dr. Tedros Ghebreyesus, WHO Director-General, Call to action for global elimination of cervical cancer, May 2018[1]

"It's not a question of can we implement HPV vaccines and should it be a public health priority, but that we would be remiss if we didn't make it a public health priority, we would be remiss in our obligations to those countries and those communities. . .now that we know that something works, you really do have a moral obligation. . ." - Program Manager of an international NGO on HPV vaccination as a health priority.[2]

Abstract

The recent rise of NCDs worldwide highlights the global burden of cancer, a burden which falls largely on the shoulders of low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). In contrast to improved detection rates and therapy in high-income countries (HICs), it is predicted that in the next decade more than ¾ths of deaths from cancer will occur in LMICs. The gap in mortality rates between LMICs and HICs can be described by several factors, including differences in educational and medical resources for the prevention of cancer. Cervical cancer is a leading example of a cancer that could be prevented, as more than 95% of cases are due to human papillomavirus. In the following narrative review of the state of oncology in LMICs, the differences in the prevention and treatment of cervical cancer in LMICs vs HICs are analyzed to provide perspective as to ways the burden of NCDs, specifically cancer, can be addressed and relieved in LMICs.

Introduction

Cancer is a leading cause of death globally, as the second leading cause of mortality from noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) responsible for over 20% of annual mortality.[[3-4]] As of 2019, cancer was the first or second leading cause of death before the age of 70 in an estimated 112 of the WHO’s 194 Member States (and the third or fourth in 23 more). The global burden of cancer incidence and mortality has been steadily increasing (Fig. 1).[5] The rising prevalence of cancer, among other NCDs, is now seen as a major threat to sustainable development, the target of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) adopted by the UN in 2015 for addressing key drivers of inequality by 2030.[[6-7]] The recent increase in prevalence and related mortality of cancer has been particularly pronounced in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). Although cancer incidence is greater in higher income countries (HICs) than in LMICs, cancer-associated mortality rates are disproportionately higher in LMICs, especially in people under 65 years of age. As of 2021, 85% of the 15 million deaths of people between the ages of 30-69 years due to NCDs (including cancer) occurred in LMICs.[8] The burden of these “premature” deaths and the cumulative loss of productive life years in LMICs has significant consequences on existing economic and health infrastructures, which already exist in fragile conditions in these countries.[6] Population statistics predict that these trends are due to worsen in the future. The concerning epidemiological trend of cancer in LMICs and vulnerability of these countries to the impacts of increased cancer mortality and incidence highlights widening inequality between the developed and developing worlds. Cancer inequities, characterized as disparities in measures of cancer control like cancer screening, incidence, morbidity and mortality between and within countries globally, call for the strengthening of health systems and cancer control programs in LMICs.[9] The challenges associated with addressing these inequities as discussed in the analysis below underscore the need for iterative development, realistic expectations, and interventions that are implemented with respect to the culture, beliefs and values, and characteristics of specific populations and countries’ healthcare and economic infrastructures.[6]

Figure 1: The rising burden of deaths due to cancer per year in LMICs versus HICs, as classified by the human development index. Data from the World Cancer Research Fund. [35]

Overview of Cancer Care in the World vs LMICs

The rise of NCDs, including cancer, globally and the WHO's call in 2013 for global action against NCDs bring attention to the status of cancer control programs across the globe. The WHO's Global Action Plan for the Prevention and Control of Noncommunicable Diseases recommended four key components for cancer control: 1) prevention, 2) early detection and diagnosis, 3) treatment, and 4) palliation. A main objective in the WHO's plan is the strengthening of health systems to address prevention and control of NCDs and their underlying social determinants through people-centered primary healthcare and universal health coverage. The provision of comprehensive care for NCDs requires access, without discrimination or financial burden, "to a nationally determined set of promotive, preventive, curative, rehabilitative and palliative basic health services."^[3] In well-resourced settings, cancer control is accomplished via health systems that offer 1) cancer screening to detect early stage cancer (precancerous lesions or preclinical cancer), 2) cancer treatment via medical therapy (e.g. chemotherapy), surgical therapy, and/or radiotherapy, and 3) palliative care and pain control. Due to the biological diversity of cancer, cancer screening and treatment require multimodal and tailored responses.^[6] For instance, while certain cancers require surgical resection, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy to treat, others may be cured with surgery alone.^[6]

The status of cancer care and infrastructure in LMICs is limited by a lack of data. The rise of NCDs in LMICs challenges health systems that have developed to combat communicable diseases, nutritional deficiencies, and maternal and child health. To address this rise, LMICs are faced with a paradigm shift in healthcare system goals and strategies. For instance, infectious disease control requires high-cost activities and can generate rapid outcomes over a short period of time, which makes it an attractive subject for humanitarian support. In contrast, the control of cancer requires long-term, sustainable initiatives with delayed medium- and long-term results.^[10] Due to the different nature of healthcare infrastructure in LMICs, the systems and strategies for cancer control in HICs are often not directly transferable to the LMIC setting. For instance, although early detection, accurate diagnosis, and tailored multimodal therapy are emphasized by the WHO for cancer control, programs for screening and early diagnosis of cancer succeed only in settings where adequate downstream services and resources are available to attend to and manage the detected cases. The limited capacity of health systems to adequately respond to early diagnoses in LMICs becomes even more problematic considering the forecasted increase in the number of cancer cases in future years. Furthermore, due to the high likelihood of cancer recurrence, additional treatment costs downstream of initial diagnosis and treatment regimens are to be expected.^[6]

Effective systems for managing and treating diagnosed cancer cases provide access to readily available and safe medical-, surgical-, and radiotherapies, as well as post-therapy monitoring and follow-up. Cancer treatment in these systems is dynamic; therapeutic decision making is informed by data on outcomes (e.g. safety and efficacy of chemotherapy), and anticancer therapy is administered and closely monitored by a multidisciplinary team for adverse effects, complications, and/or tumor response (e.g. through computed tomography, magnetic resonance imaging, and/or positron emission tomography scanning).^[6] Data on therapy outcomes are for the most part not readily available in LMICs, as some LMICs do not have the capacity to perform their own clinical trials, and data from HICs is not always applicable, especially considering how performance can vary with different tumor biology, population characteristics, or specific environmental determinants.^[6] The availability of anticancer therapies in LMICs is another question. A study in Mexico showed that over 80% of the population experienced barriers to accessing innovative medicines that could improve their treatment outcomes.^[11]

A 2017 study showed that in LMICs, 5.2% of medicines on the WHO’s Model of Essential Medicines List (EML) were not available at all and 32.0% were only available at full cost.[12] An earlier WHO survey found that only 22% of African countries and 43% of Southeast Asian countries reported availability of anticancer therapy (compared to over 90% availability reported in Europe).[13] A 2011 WHO report found that 20% to 60% of health expenditures in developing and transitional countries were for medicines, allocations greatly exceeding those in developed countries. Second to food, medicines were found to be the single largest out-of-pocket expenditure for families in developing countries.[6] In addition to financial barriers, drug shortages commonly plague access in LMICs. Human capacity (medical and surgical specialists, trained nurses, and pharmacists, for example) and resource capacity (hospital beds, antibiotics, imaging modalities, and supportive therapies like blood transfusions) are also critical to meet the rising cancer burden in LMICs. Little is known about the existing capacities of health system infrastructure and the health workforce for cancer control in LMICs.[6] Surgical services are not available to a majority of the world's population (Table 1): an estimated 5 billion people lack access to affordable surgical services when needed, and an estimated 33 million people face financial ruin from surgery and anesthesia payments each year.[6] Radiotherapy is also largely inaccessible in LMICs (Table 1), leaving the 5 million new people estimated to need radiation therapy each year in LMICs unaddressed.[14] A 2006 study reported that 22 African and Asian countries did not have access to radiotherapy at all and that the supply in Africa accounted for only 18% of total radiation needs.[15]

Table 1: Percentage ranges of countries with generally available cancer diagnosis and treatment services in the public sector, by World Bank income group (2010). Data from the global strategy to accelerate the elimination of cervical cancer as a public health problem [2].

Countries with Cancer Management Services Available					
	Cancer centers at tertiary level	Pathology services	Cancer Surgery	Chemotherapy	Radiotherapy
High-income	90-95%	95-100%	95-100%	95-100%	90-95%
Higher-middle-income	85-90%	90-95%	90-95%	80-85%	65-70%
Lower-middle-income	65-70%	70-75%	65-70%	65-70%	45-50%
Low-income	30-35%	35-40%	25-30%	25-30%	15-20%

Although LMICs experience 70% of total deaths from cancer, and 80% of the burden from these deaths (measured by disability-adjusted life years, DALYs), they share less than 5% of the global resources for combating cancer.[16] Going forward, four priorities have been proposed for improving cancer care and data collection in LMICs: 1) expand health services research, policy, and planning tailored to the LMIC context, 2) establish health data sources (for instance, population-based cancer registries, PBCRs) to measure the outcomes and quality of cancer control, 3) perform economic evaluations of oncology outcomes in LMICs, and 4) explore cancer control models in the LMIC setting. To make progress towards these priorities, resources, policy changes, and transparent communication will be required; models approximate that the budget for health services and policy research will need to expand from 0.007% to 0.1% of the total healthcare expenditure in LMICs.[6] The human and monetary resources that will be needed to prioritize cancer care in LMICs are by no means insignificant and make cancer control a global health challenge that enlists the commitment of industry leaders.[6]

Cervical cancer in LMICs

The widening gap in cancer mortality rates between LMICs and HICs can be explained in part by the educational resources, increased number of screening and surveillance programs that result in earlier detection of disease, improved cancer therapies, and better risk factor control in HICs. The risk of persistent carcinogenic infection disproportionately affects LMICs. Whereas infection-related cancer mortality is rare in HICs, infection associated cancer accounts for a fourth of all cancer cases in less developed countries.[6,17] 15% of all new cancer cases each year are caused by infectious agents, and two-thirds of these cases occur in less developed countries. This disparity is particularly concerning as up to a third of infection-attributable cancer arises in young people under the age of 50, contributing to the number of premature deaths and economic burden caused by cancer in LMICs.[6]

The human papillomavirus (HPV) is the primary cause of cervical cancer, which is the fourth most common cancer among women globally and the leading cause of cancer death among women in many less-developed parts of the world.[17] More than 95% of cervical cancer cases are due to HPV, which is primarily transmitted through sexual contact. While cervical cancer has been relatively well controlled for several decades in many HICs due to cervical screening initiatives and effective cancer treatment services, it is the most common cause of cancer-related death among women in 42 countries, the majority of which being LMICs.[18] In 2020, 90% of new cervical cancer cases and deaths occurred in LMICs, with India alone accounting for 25% of the total cases (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3).[19] Cervical cancer is unique as it is one of the most preventable and treatable forms of cancer. Specifically, vaccines against HPV are effective in protecting against the oncogenic HPV serotypes that are responsible for about 90% of all cervical cancers, and thus can prevent persistent HPV infection and its associated cervical cancer risk.[17] In LMICs, many of the deaths from cervical cancer occur due to limited access to preventative measures, screening, and treatment of cancerous lesions. It takes persistent infection and between 15 to 20 years for cervical cancer to develop in women with normal immune systems, and cervical cancer can be cured if diagnosed at an early stage and treated promptly.[1] The treatment and prevention of cervical cancer in LMICs is a highly relevant topic that illuminates the challenges of implementing the kind of multilevel policy interventions in LMICs that are needed to reduce cancer inequities, as well as gender inequality at large.

Figure 2: Estimated age-standardized cervical cancer incidence rate in females of all ages (2020). (Generated using GLOBOCAN 2020) [22]

Figure 3: Estimated age-standardized cervical cancer mortality rates in females of all ages (2020). (Generated using GLOBOCAN 2020) [22]

In 2020, the World Health Assembly adopted the Global Strategy for cervical cancer elimination in response to the Director-General’s call in 2018 for all countries to help end the suffering caused by cervical cancer, marking the first global commitment to eliminate a specific cancer. The strategy has set the following 90-70-90 targets that will need to be met by 2030 and maintained to achieve the elimination of cervical cancer: 90% of girls fully vaccinated with HPV vaccine by age 15 years, 70% of women screened with a high-performance test by age 35 and again by age 45, and 90% of women identified with cervical disease treated (90% of women with precancer treated, and 90% of women with invasive cancer managed). Elimination of cervical cancer as a public health problem has been defined by an incidence threshold of 4 per 100,000 women per year. The Global Strategy aligns with Sustainable Development and the principle of leaving no one behind, supporting several SDGs. The strategy proposes a trio of comprehensive cancer control initiatives: primary prevention by means of vaccination, secondary prevention through screening and treatment of precancerous lesions, and tertiary prevention through diagnosis and treatment of invasive cervical cancer, followed by palliative care.[2] This strategy emphasizes a life-course approach that follows girls from adolescence through adulthood and implements multidisciplinary cancer prevention through community education, social mobilization, vaccination, screening, treatment, and palliative care.[1]

Because the primary cause of precancerous and cancerous cervical lesions is infection with a high-risk or oncogenic HPV serotype, primary prevention targets girls ages 9-14 years for vaccination against the subset of HPV serotypes responsible for cervical cancer. More than 100 virus types that are common worldwide are included in the group known as HPV and 14 of these are oncogenic, with serotypes 16 and 18 together linked to 70% of cervical cancer cases worldwide. Cervical HPV is the most common sexually transmitted infection (STI), and the pathogenesis of cervical cancer is the same worldwide. The first prophylactic HPV vaccine was licensed in 2006. By 2017, more than 100 million adolescent girls had received at least one dose of the HPV vaccine, 95% of whom were born in HICs. Access to vaccination is improving as in 2019, more than 65% of girls vaccinated each year across the globe were living in LMICs. However, access to cervical cancer screening programs and cancer management services in LMICs is still lagging (x 1 and 2). While more than 85% of HICs had introduced the HPV vaccine into their national immunization schedule by 2020, less than 25% of low-income countries (LICs) and less than 30% of LMICs had. As of 2020, pathology services, cancer surgery, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy are generally available in the public sectors of approximately 30% of LMICs, compared to more than 90% of HICs (Table 1).[2]

The Global Strategy's first intervention is for the primary prevention of cervical cancer through HPV vaccination, which is the most effective, long-term intervention for reducing the risk of developing cervical cancer.[2] There is evidence that vaccination not only has long term benefit, but that high coverage can protect unvaccinated individuals through herd immunity. The 2030 target of 90% coverage of young adolescent girls between ages 9 and 14 with two doses aims to address the inequitable distribution of HPV vaccine coverage across different geographies and income levels. This will require that several underlying determinants are addressed, including high vaccine prices and supply challenges that are often associated with countries' inability to introduce and sustain national immunization programs. Additionally, improved communication strategies are needed for social mobilization, advocacy for the safety, efficacy, and benefits of the vaccine, and to counter the rising antivaccination movement. Information around sexual and reproductive health, safer sexual practices, and cessation of tobacco use is also fundamental to widespread HPV vaccination of adolescents and to empower adolescents to take ownership of their health and wellbeing. [[2,20]]

The Global Strategy's second intervention is for secondary prevention by means of screening of women over 30 years (with priority to those between 30 and 49) and treatment for precancerous lesions. As primary prevention measures through vaccination do not account for the two-to-three generations that have not received the vaccine or already have the infection, and widespread vaccination coverage has yet to be achieved, screening is important for preventing cervical cancer in these populations.[19] Testing is the preferred method universally recommended by the WHO, as it carries a strong negative predictive value and is highly accessible. For instance, self-sampling is an option with testing, and technological platforms in use for HIV, TB, and other infections can be used for HPV testing. Screening initiatives will require affordable and high-quality diagnostics and supplies and that the increased levels of detected lesions can be met with the capacity for treatment. Cryotherapy, in which cells are destroyed with extreme cold, is the preferred treatment option for precancerous lesions in screening in all settings, due to its affordability and easy implementation.[19]

The Global Strategy's third intervention is for tertiary prevention through treatment. Invasive cervical cancer is typically treated with surgery or radiation, sometimes combined with chemotherapy, although these modalities require access to specialized healthcare providers and other services like pathology and medical imaging that are limited to high-resource settings. [[19,2]] Most patients in LMICs present at stages that require radiation therapy, and radiation therapy and surgery with or without chemotherapy can often cure early stage cancer; cervical cancer survival rates in countries with timely diagnosis and high quality treatment exceed 80%.[2] To establish the multidisciplinary teams that characterize modern cancer care, workforce challenges will need to be addressed. For instance, long-term national health workforce education training, recruitment, and retention, and postgraduate training for areas like surgery, radiology, pathology, and patient consultation will be needed. Strategies for strengthening national workforces include North-South twinning partnerships, tele-mentoring, regional training hubs, and e-learning. An integral part of cervical cancer treatment is the care of cancer survivors. For instance, in sub-Saharan Africa, the quality of life of cancer survivors is most negatively impacted by a lack of social support, primarily from spouses. Comprehensive support to patients and survivors, encompassing physical, psychological, social, and spiritual care, as well as efforts to reduce cancer stigmatization through patient awareness, health literacy, and education initiatives in survivor groups, can have a significant positive impact on quality of life.[2]

Progress towards cervical cancer elimination

Countries have been making various progress towards the 2030 elimination targets Over the past

4-6 decades, cervical cancer incidence and mortality have dramatically decreased in HICs due to high coverage of screening, precancer treatment, and cancer management.[19] In some HICs, cervical cancer incidence has decreased as much as 80% (Fig. 4). Incidence rates also declined in some LMICs (such as in Colombia, the Philippines, and India) between 1975 and 2007, likely due to improved screening activities and socioeconomic conditions, however rates have been increasing in recent years (Fig. 4).[21] Despite some progress, more than 300,000 women have died each year from cervical cancer since the WHO Director-General’s call to action in 2018 - deaths that could have been entirely prevented. There are approximately 600,000 new cases of cervical cancer each year, with most of the disease burden and death occurring in LMICs and poor, remote, and marginalized populations in countries. The highest cervical cancer incidence and mortality rates are in sub-Saharan Africa, Central and South America, South Eastern Asia, and Central and Eastern Europe.[[19,22]] Cervical cancer rates have increased over the past few decades in Uganda, Zimbabwe, and some countries of Central and Eastern Europe, and among younger women in many countries of Europe, Japan, and China. These increases are hypothesized to reflect changing sexual practices and increased HPV prevalence paired with inadequate screening.[19] In terms of the primary prevention goals outlined by the WHO for HPV vaccination, only 3% of countries had reached the 90% coverage target by 2019 and just 23% of countries had greater than 50% program coverage. As of 2019, 65% of countries had cervical screening programs (Table 2), but only 12% of countries reached the coverage target of more than 70%. Furthermore, only 7% of countries use the preferred DNA test for screening and only 40% of countries have organized, population-based screening programs.[23] Comprehensive health services for tertiary cervical cancer prevention through treatment are widely implemented in HICs (>90% of HICs) but are rarer in LICs (<15% of LICs).[21]

Figure 4: Cervical cancer mortality and incidence rates between 1990 and 2019. (General using The Global Health Data Exchange) [36]

HPV vaccination coverage is a key indicator of progress towards cervical cancer elimination as it conveys the performance of national vaccination programs and can forecast the future of reduced HPV-related disease burden.[22] Since the HPV vaccine became available in 2006 and was recommended by the WHO in 2009, countries have progressively introduced the vaccine into their national immunization schedules. Prior to the WHO Director-General’s global call for action in 2018, it was estimated that only 6% of girls worldwide were vaccinated by 2014 and that only 12% were targeted by national programs in 2016. By June 2020, 107 of the WHO’s 194 member states had introduced HPV vaccination. However, there is not an equal geographic distribution of vaccination implementation. The greatest number of introductions have been in the Americas and Europe, with 85% and 77% of countries implementing programs, respectively. It took less than a decade for 80% of HICs to introduce the HPV vaccine. LMICs, which outnumber HICs by at least two to one, in contrast lag far behind, with only 41% of LMICs having introduced a vaccination program by the end of 2019. This gap seems to be shrinking however, as in 2019, a record number of introductions were observed, 87% of which were in LMICs (Fig. 5).[24]

Figure 5: Cumulative number of countries that had introduced HPV vaccination by 2019, according to sex, year, and income level. Data from Bruni et al., 2021. [24]

Program performance is suboptimal in many countries (including in well-resourced HICs): overall, average coverage for the first dose is around 67% and 53% for the final dose. LMICs have a greater first dose coverage than HICs (80% vs 72% coverage, respectively) but a lower last dose coverage due to higher dropout (18% vs 11% dropout rate). The sustainability of program performance in LMICs is in question as programs age and delivery strategies evolve. As of 2019, only 5 (6%) of countries reached the 90% coverage target, whereas 22 (21%) reached greater than 75% coverage and 35 (40%) had 50% coverage or less (Fig. 6). These coverage levels starkly contrast to Diphtheria, Tetanus, and Pertussis vaccination (DTP3) levels as only a minority of countries globally (3%) report coverage levels below 50%. An estimated 15% of girls and 4% of boys globally had received the final HPV vaccine dose by 2019, and 20% and 5% of girls and boys respectively had received at least one dose (Fig. 7). Although more than half of the world’s countries have introduced the vaccine, 70% of girls are located in countries that have not introduced the vaccine. These countries include China, India, Nigeria, Pakistan, Indonesia, Bangladesh, and Russia (Fig. 4). As of 2019, Australia and New Zealand, and Latin America achieved the highest final dose coverages, whereas Northern Africa, Oceania (minus Australia and New Zealand), and Asia all had exceptionally low coverage rates.

Notably, sub-Saharan Africa had already achieved nearly 20% coverage by 2019 from national programs that have been introduced, accounting for only a third of the countries in the region. Global coverage has been gradually increasing; however, this trend is thought to be the result of the increasing number of countries that are introducing vaccine programs rather than the improvement of program performance.[24]

Figure 6: Coverage estimates for HPV vaccination programs for girls in 2019 for LMICs. Data from Bruni et al., 2021.[24]

Figure 7: Global estimates of HPV vaccination coverage by age 15 years between 2010 and 2019. Data from Bruni et al., 2021.[24]

Cervical cancer as an indicator of inequality

The decline in worldwide cervical cancer rates that has been observed from 1990 until 2019 can be attributed to the introduction of precautionary procedures, including access to HPV vaccination, healthcare, and education, as well as sociocultural factors, such as changes in marriage age and family planning behavior. Underneath this global trend, however, vast disparities still exist at the inter- and intra-country levels.[25] Cervical cancer is the cancer with the largest inter-country variability; many African countries have incidence and mortality rates at least 10-to-20 fold higher than those in several West Asian, Middle Eastern, and European countries.[26] While many industrialized countries experienced declining trends in cervical cancer rates over the past few decades, these trends have been significantly less pronounced or nonexistent in much of the developing world, where certain countries still experience increasing rates.

For instance, in Lesotho, increasing rates of cervical cancer are a result of socio-economic and -cultural challenges including poverty, weak health systems, and low education levels. In contrast, huge government expenditure for robust HPV vaccination and screening programs have been cited as reasons for the most drastic declines in cervical cancer incidence seen in the Maldives, Taiwan, and Singapore.[25] Singh et al. (2012) found that HDI and poverty each explained >52% of the global variance in cervical cancer mortality and that higher healthcare expenditure levels per capita were independently associated with decreased incidence and mortality risks.[26] In addition, broader social determinants such as gender inequality index (GII), urbanization, material living conditions, and literacy rate were also significantly related to cervical cancer incidence and mortality.[26]

Gender inequality is particularly relevant in the context of cervical cancer, as cervical cancer is the leading cause of death among women in many less-developed countries.[1] Furthermore, cervical cancer rates are rising in younger women in many developing countries. Global inequality analysis has uncovered the concerning trend that cervical cancer tends to target younger women (<45) more than the other major cancers, exacerbating existing inequality by causing high years-of-life-loss (YLL) among women especially in developing countries. A 0.2 unit increase in GII was shown to increase the risk of cervical cancer diagnosis and prevented death by 24% and 42%, respectively. 24% and 33% of global variance in incidence and mortality rates respectively could be explained by GII. Women in countries with low gender equality and high cervical cancer rates, such as Guinea, Comoros, and Zambia, have overall lower levels of reproductive health, educational attainment, empowerment, and workforce participation than women in more egalitarian countries.[26] As cervical cancer is a disease that predominantly and disproportionately affects women, its elimination as a public health burden carries even more weight in the global context. The prioritization of the health of women and girls and the reduction of gender inequality at large are critical contexts in which the elimination of cervical cancer exists. The elimination of cervical cancer should be just as much a fight against drivers of gender inequality as a fight to end a public health burden. The drivers of gender inequality that must be addressed include, but are not limited to, 1) countries' reluctance to invest in women's health as a public expenditure,[27] 2) sexual- and gender-based violence which significantly raises risk of cervical cancer and perpetuates disease spread,[[28]] 3) stigma around women diagnosed with cancer,[[29]] and 4) poor community support or rejection of women diagnosed with cancer from their homes or communities. [[30]] The failure of countries to address cervical cancer is a failure to acknowledge the societal value of women, which when economically quantified dramatically outweighs the financial investment needed to scale up cervical cancer prevention and treatment interventions in high-burden countries between 2018 and 2030. Specifically, 10.5 billion US dollars (USD) are estimated by the WHO to be needed for the scale up, whereas the survival and retention of 250,000 women as productive members of the workforce upon cervical cancer elimination would add an estimated 28 billion USD to the world's economy.[2]

A woman with cervical cancer is a sign of a fragile health care system. Specifically, a woman with cervical cancer is a woman whose disease was not prevented with HPV vaccination or diagnosed at an early stage with screening and subsequently treated or was diagnosed but inadequately treated. In other words, a woman with cervical cancer is a woman that has been missed by the healthcare system, whether for lack of access (ex. financial access or physical access and transportation), lack of services, or lack of support (ex. fear of stigmatization, community or family rejection, or disapproval by partner). Global inequalities in cervical cancer mortality are much larger than those in cervical cancer incidence. These inequalities reflect disparities in patient survival rates, disease stage at diagnosis, and access to health services and cancer treatments.[26] The extent of disease at diagnosis, particularly late-stage cancer diagnosis, is a marker for worse prognosis. 32

This is particularly true for women in developing countries where there is a lack of screening or of treatment services for more advanced cancer types. For instance, 81% of patients in Singapore were diagnosed at an early, localized stage, compared to 7% in Chennai, India.[26] Low socioeconomic conditions and levels of human development are seen to indicate under-resourced health systems, and limited capacity for public health improvement and cancer prevention and control efforts. Inequalities within the health care system are captured in cervical cancer outcomes. Within countries, rural and socioeconomically disadvantaged women are much less likely to be screened; globally, women in the poorest wealth decile are 7 times less likely to receive cervical cancer compared to their affluent peers.[26] Well-resourced patients are more likely to catch their disease in an early stage and have access to treatment. In contrast, poorly resourced patients are less likely to have access to screening services or healthcare to catch early-stage disease. Patients become delineated across socioeconomic lines and outcomes are discriminated by access regardless of a patient's motivation to seek care. Thus, in fragile health care systems where access is not universal, women's knowledge and attitudes can do little to prevent low levels of program efficacy or late diagnosis.[10] High rates of cervical cancer incidence and mortality in countries reflect the failure of countries to implement prevention, screening, and treatment services. This phenomenon and its underlying factors emphasize the importance of strong and synergized cervical cancer programs for vaccination, screening, and treatment, healthcare systems, and patient and community attitudes and information regarding cervical cancer.

Strategies for the elimination of cervical cancer

The elimination of cervical cancer is thus a strongly motivated public health and human rights initiative that is critical for sustainable development. Elimination strategies in LMICs should be keenly prioritized and can benefit from analysis of the status-quo of HPV vaccination efforts and cancer control infrastructure in LMICs, as well as from research projects designed in these countries or in low-income settings. The WHO's Global Strategy for achieving cervical cancer elimination includes tactics to reach the 2030 targets for vaccination, screening, and treatment coverage. In addition, the following three strategic objectives are recommended to achieve elimination:

1) strengthen health systems, 2) improve data surveillance, monitoring, and evaluation, and 3) leverage partnerships, advocacy, and communication.[2] Other areas of the literature reinforce these objectives and practical actions for cervical cancer elimination can be discerned from case studies that analyze the introduction and implementation of national vaccination programs in different LMICs.

Strategic actions for each of the three stages of cervical cancer control have been proposed by the WHO. Whereas cervical cancer prevention is largely a campaign for widespread vaccination and can be implemented independently of broad health care reform, cervical cancer screening and treatment are more dependent on the strength of the health system. Health systems must have robust infrastructure to support screening and treatment, including a trained and retained workforce for service delivery, surgery, radiology, pathology, and patient consultation; sufficient medical devices (ex. linear accelerators for external beam radiation therapy); modern lab platforms; readily available anesthetic services; intensive care units; and blood banks for instance. Access to healthcare and patient motivation to uptake services are also required for screening and treating cervical cancer and can be compromised by social, cultural, societal, and structural barriers.[2] Universal health coverage is seen as a fundamental action for enabling access to cervical cancer care in LMICs, and a primary healthcare approach, in which care is people-centered and streamlined, is recommended as the most effective way to address the demands of cervical cancer control.[2,21]

Strategies for HPV vaccination

The first step towards cervical cancer elimination is to improve disease prevention through HPV

vaccination. Vaccination is one of the most efficacious and cost-effective interventions available. Most cervical cancer cases can be prevented by vaccinating adolescent girls before sexual debut and first exposure to HPV infection. In general, prevention-focused campaigns against infection-based cancers are relatively low-cost, high impact interventions and are seen as a positive step towards reducing global cancer burden. In contrast, early diagnosis does not have much bearing on mortality if existing treatments (including surgery, chemotherapy, and radiotherapy) are not effective or inaccessible.[6] Likewise, cancer control programs and experiences in resource replete settings are not universally extrapolatable to resource constrained settings. Screening programs that aim to detect early disease assume that there are adequate downstream resources available to manage the increased number of diagnosed preclinical cases. Without healthcare infrastructure to handle the increased number of cases with appropriate treatment, support, and follow-up, screening programs may be premature, and moreover, unethical. The WHO has published 10 key criteria to meet before screening is implemented, which include having scientific evidence of screening program effectiveness, and that the benefits of screening outweigh potential harms. The harms of screening can extend beyond the physical risks of procedures. Cancer diagnosis often causes great psychological burden, especially in communities where cancer is believed to be incurable, and universally fatal and patients are stigmatized and ostracized, as well as can cause financial hardship, from expensive downstream diagnostic and therapeutic interventions.[6] Modeling studies have suggested that HPV vaccination can reduce the incidence and mortality of cervical cancer and the incidence of abnormal diagnostic tests and precancerous cervical lesions that require expensive medical follow-up and treatment, and be cost effective in some LMICs with no or limited screening.[31] It is proposed that LMICs introducing cervical cancer programs will have to consider whether to invest in both screening and vaccination.[27] At this crossroads, the prevention of cervical cancer by means of vaccination can arguably be seen as the practical first step.

The costs of HPV vaccination programs are a major challenge for a majority of LMICs. 59% of the 10.5 billion USD budget estimated to finance the WHO strategy for 2030 is estimated to be needed for vaccination programs, especially at program startup. The actual costs of the vaccine are responsible for greater than half of these costs (51%), as each dose to the public sector ranges from \$13 to \$100 USD. [[27,32]] Additional direct medical costs are associated with cold chain, staff education, monitoring and evaluation, social mobilization, and vaccination campaigns. Hence, subsidies to reduce the price of vaccines can be very influential in supporting coverage or vaccine introduction in LMICs.[10]

Gavi has supported HPV vaccination demonstration projects or national immunization programs in 53 Gavi-eligible countries, and vaccines have been donated through the GARDASIL® Access Program (GAP), manufacturer partnerships (ex. with Merck), and the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation through PATH.[27,33] Other large-volume vaccine purchasers, such as UNICEF and PAHO, have a history of negotiating lower vaccine prices for low-resource countries, and can failsafe global supply by promoting vaccine manufacture scale up.[31] Partnerships with these international NGOs have demonstrated high vaccine uptake from key starting steps. These steps include identifying the size of the HPV target population based on available data, for instance for birth cohort, student grades, or headcounts; developing training modules for vaccinators; and mobilizing social support from the community including from parents, the village, and religious leaders.[32] Strategies to reduce delivery costs include integrating HPV vaccination into existing health services, and using school-based delivery as the primary approach. Overtime although the costs to scale up vaccination coverage may increase, the cost of training personnel and of social mobilization may decline, as was observed in Mozambique.

Although international support can be critical to vaccine introduction in countries, the transition away from NGO support to national funding often challenges the sustainability of programs, as evidenced by the drop in vaccination uptake in countries after funding withdrawal.[32,33] For instance, 34 studies from 17 countries that reported overall high vaccine uptake (>50%) had uptake drop from approximately 89.03% (pooled vaccine uptake) in the female-only vaccination period from 2006-2014

to 41.48% in the gender-neutral vaccination period after 2014.[32] To better the transition from external to national support, policymakers have requested data and/or technical assistance to compare the relative costs and sustainability of different HPV vaccination strategies.[33] These requests emphasize how important it is for NGO-assisted demonstration programs to reflect the country's specific needs and capacities. Surveillance systems can be useful here, as they can help countries better allocate resources, manage costs, and track the progress of HPV vaccination, screening, and treatment programs.[9]

Conclusion

As cancer incidence rises in the future, the mobilization of resources and strengthening of health systems to provide comprehensive cancer care and disease control will be even more critical to Sustainable Development. Within this context, cervical cancer takes great precedence as a disease that exacerbates existing inequality and remains a major threat to public health – despite its being entirely preventable.[34] The unnecessary loss of life due to cervical cancer underscores the moral obligation to make cervical cancer elimination a global health priority. The elimination of cervical cancer not only addresses a public health burden, but also systemically acknowledges cancer inequities and the disproportionate burden of disease and death experienced by LMICs. Furthermore, cervical cancer elimination addresses not only cancer inequities, but gender inequality at large and raises global commitment to prioritize and invest in the health and wellbeing of women and girls.

References

1. Cervical cancer. Accessed September 18, 2024. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cervical-cancer>
2. Global strategy to accelerate the elimination of cervical cancer as a public health problem. Accessed September 18, 2024. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240014107>
3. Global action plan for the prevention and control of noncommunicable diseases 2013-2020. Accessed September 18, 2024. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241506236>
4. Cancer. Accessed September 18, 2024. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/cancer>
5. Sung H, Ferlay J, Siegel RL, et al. Global Cancer Statistics 2020: GLOBOCAN Estimates of Incidence and Mortality Worldwide for 36 Cancers in 185 Countries. *CA Cancer J Clin.* 2021;71(3):209-249. doi:10.3322/caac.21660
6. Shah SC, Kayamba V, Peek RM, Heimbürger D. Cancer Control in Low- and Middle-Income Countries: Is It Time to Consider Screening? *J Glob Oncol.* 2019;(5):1-8. doi:10.1200/JGO.18.00200
7. Sustainable Development Goals. UNDP. Accessed September 18, 2024. <https://www.undp.org/sustainable-development-goals>
8. Non communicable diseases. Accessed September 18, 2024. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/noncommunicable-diseases>
9. List JM, O'Connor JM. How Should Low- and Middle-Income Countries Motivate Equity in Cancer Prevention and Control? *AMA J Ethics.* 2020;22(2):147-155. doi:10.1001/amajethics.2020.147
10. Vale DB, Teixeira JC, Bragança JF, Derchain S, Sarian LO, Zeferino LC. Elimination of cervical cancer in low- and middle-income countries: Inequality of access and fragile healthcare systems. *Int J Gynecol Obstet.* 2021;152(1):7-11. doi:10.1002/ijgo.13458
11. Moye-Holz D, Soria Saucedo R, van Dijk JP, Reijneveld SA, Hogerzeil HV. Access to innovative cancer medicines in a middle-income country - the case of Mexico. *J Pharm Policy Pract.* 2018;11(1):25. doi:10.1186/s40545-018-0153-y
12. Ocran Mattila P, Ahmad R, Hasan SS, Babar ZUD. Availability, Affordability, Access, and Pricing of Anti-cancer Medicines in Low- and Middle-Income Countries: A Systematic Review of Literature. *Front Public Health.* 2021;9. doi:10.3389/fpubh.2021.628744
13. Assessment of National Capacity for Noncommunicable Disease Prevention and Control: The Report of a Global Survey. Accessed September 18, 2024. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/WHO-MNC-01.2>
14. International Atomic Energy Agency. A Silent Crisis: Cancer Treatment in Developing Countries. IAEA; 2003:20.
15. Barton MB, Frommer M, Shafiq J. Role of radiotherapy in cancer control in low-income and middle-income countries. *Lancet Oncol.* 2006;7(7):584-595. doi:10.1016/S1470-2045(06)70759-8
16. Organization WH. Technical Report: Pricing of Cancer Medicines and Its Impacts: A Comprehensive Technical Report for the World Health Assembly Resolution 70.12: Operative Paragraph 2.9 on Pricing Approaches and Their Impacts on Availability and Affordability of Medicines for the Prevention and Treatment of Cancer. World Health Organization; 2018. Accessed September 18, 2024. <https://iris.who.int/handle/10665/277190>
17. Infection. The Cancer Atlas. Accessed September 18, 2024. <http://canceratlas.cancer.org/NnW>
18. Canfell K, Kim JJ, Brisson M, et al. Mortality impact of achieving WHO cervical cancer elimination targets: a comparative modelling analysis in 78 low-income and lower-middle-income countries. *The Lancet.* 2020;395(10224):591-603. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(20)30157-4
19. Torre LA, Islami F, Siegel RL, Ward EM, Jemal A. Global Cancer in Women: Burden and Trends. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev.* 2017;26(4):444-457. doi:10.1158/1055-9965.EPI-16-0858
20. Amponsah-Dacosta E, Blose N, Nkwini VV, Chepkurui V. Human Papillomavirus Vaccination in South Africa: Programmatic Challenges and Opportunities for Integration With Other Adolescent Health Services? *Front Public Health.* 2022;10. doi:10.3389/fpubh.2022.799984
21. Torode J, Kithaka B, Chowdhury R, Simelela N, Cruz JL, Tsu VD. National action towards a world free of cervical cancer for all women. *Prev Med.* 2021;144:106313. doi:10.1016/j.ypmed.2020.106313
22. Cancer Today. Accessed September 18, 2024. <https://gco.iarc.who.int/today/>
23. WHO report on cancer: setting priorities, investing wisely and providing care for all. Accessed September 18, 2024. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240001299>
24. Bruni L, Saura-Lázaro A, Montoliu A, et al. HPV vaccination introduction worldwide and WHO and UNICEF estimates of national HPV immunization coverage 2010-2019. *Prev Med.* 2021;144:106399. doi:10.1016/j.ypmed.2020.106399

25. Zhang X, Zeng Q, Cai W, Ruan W. Trends of cervical cancer at global, regional, and national level: data from the Global Burden of Disease study 2019. *BMC Public Health*. 2021;21(1):894. doi:10.1186/s12889-021-10907-5
26. Singh GK, Azuine RE, Siahpush M. Global Inequalities in Cervical Cancer Incidence and Mortality are Linked to Deprivation, Low Socioeconomic Status, and Human Development. *Int J MCH AIDS*. 2012;1(1):17-30. doi:10.21106/ijma.12
27. Wigle J, Coast E, Watson-Jones D. Human papillomavirus (HPV) vaccine implementation in low and middle-income countries (LMICs): Health system experiences and prospects. *Vaccine*. 2013;31(37):3811-3817. doi:10.1016/j.vaccine.2013.06.016
28. Coker AL, Hopenhayn C, DeSimone CP, Bush HM, Crofford L. Violence against Women Raises Risk of Cervical Cancer. *J Womens Health*. 2009;18(8):1179-1185. doi:10.1089/jwh.2008.1048
29. Ginjupalli R, Mundaden R, Choi Y, et al. Developing a framework to describe stigma related to cervical cancer and HPV in western Kenya. *BMC Womens Health*. 2022;22(1):39. doi:10.1186/s12905-022-01619-y
30. Tillyard G, Surena G, Cornely JR, Mondestin MJ, Senatus D, DeGennaro Jr V. A mixed methods, community-based investigation on women's cancer awareness in Haiti. *Health Soc Care Community*. 2019;27(6):1458-1468. doi:10.1111/hsc.12817
31. Organization WH. Cervical cancer, human papillomavirus (HPV) and HPV vaccines: key points for policy-makers and health professionals. Published online 2008. Accessed September 18, 2024. <https://iris.who.int/handle/10665/69873>
32. Dorji T, Nopsopon T, Tamang ST, Pongpirul K. Human papillomavirus vaccination uptake in low-and middle-income countries: a meta-analysis. *EClinicalMedicine*. 2021;34:100836. doi:10.1016/j.eclinm.2021.100836
33. Gallagher KE, Howard N, Kabakama S, et al. Human papillomavirus (HPV) vaccine coverage achievements in low and middle-income countries 2007–2016. *Papillomavirus Res*. 2017;4:72-78. doi:10.1016/j.pvr.2017.09.001
34. Focus on cancer: NIH supports cancer research to reduce disease burden - Fogarty International Center @ NIH. Fogarty International Center. Accessed September 18, 2024. <https://www.fic.nih.gov:443/News/GlobalHealthMatters/july-august-2018/Pages/nih-research-reduce-global-cancer-burden.aspx>
35. Cancer rates by Human Development Index. WCRF International. Accessed August 19, 2024. <https://www.wcrf.org/cancer-trends/cancer-rates-human-development-index/>
36. Global Health Data Exchange | GHDx. Accessed September 18, 2024. <https://ghdx.healthdata.org/>

The Association Between Food Insecurity and Parental Feeding Practices Prior To, and During, the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Scoping Review

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Abstract

Background: Food insecurity (FI) is associated with parental feeding behaviors. The COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated food insecurity, particularly among families with children.

Objective: Summarize literature on parental feeding practices in the context of FI both prior to, and during, the COVID-19 pandemic.

Methods: A scoping review study was conducted. Terms related to FI and parental feeding practices were used to search literature published January 1, 2012 – April 21, 2023. Databases included MEDLINE (PubMed), EMBASE (Elsevier), PsycINFO (EBSCO), Cochrane Central (OVID), and Scopus (Elsevier). Eligible studies included (1) households in the U.S. with children under 18 and (2) identification of FI and parental feeding practices using validated survey tools. All studies were reviewed by two independent reviewers. Results were analyzed qualitatively.

Results: Seventeen studies were included. Eleven were conducted pre-pandemic and six during the pandemic. FI was frequently measured using a version of the United States Department of Agriculture Household Food Security Survey Module. Studies used a variety of different survey tools to evaluate feeding practices. Evidence was mixed. Several studies described a positive statistically significant association between FI and controlling parental feeding practices, with an increase in pressured feeding behaviors during the pandemic. Several studies conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic also noted increased parental concern for child weight, with specific concern that children may be overweight.

Conclusion: FI may be associated with greater controlling parental feeding practices. Published research on parental feeding practices since the COVID-19 pandemic is limited. Future research is needed in this area given the increased prevalence of FI among families with children during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Introduction

In 2020, 14.8% of households in the United States (U.S.) with children under 18 years experienced food insecurity (FI). [1] FI is a “household-level economic and social condition of limited or uncertain access to adequate food.” [2] FI is associated with poor health outcomes among children such as obesity, psychological stress, poor nutrition, growth, and development.[3–6] FI may influence parental feeding practices and may be associated with obesity.[7,8] Parental feeding– specific behaviors and actions employed, intentionally or not, to modify a child’s eating behavior– are important in shaping a child’s diet quality, eating behaviors, and growth.[9,10] There are several frameworks and terms used to describe parental feeding practices in the literature. For the purpose of this review, we defined parental feeding practices as follows: controlling feeding practices – such as pressure to eat and restriction of food – which are considered maladaptive eating behaviors. [11] Monitoring – in which a parent tracks what and how much a child eats to ensure sufficient intake of healthy foods and avoid unhealthy foods, is a non-coercive feeding practice thought to be a more positive approach. [10]

FI has been exacerbated during the COVID-19 pandemic. FI in households with children rose from 13.6% in 2019 to 14.8% in 2020. [1,12] Given the detrimental influence of FI on the growth and development of children and its association with parental feeding behaviors, the objective of our scoping review was to 1) summarize the literature on the association between FI and parental feeding behaviors prior to the COVID-19 pandemic and 2) summarize the association between FI and parental feeding behaviors during the COVID-19 pandemic

Methods

Scope of the review

A scoping review was chosen to map available evidence. Given the relative recency of the COVID-19 pandemic, a scoping review was determined as the ideal research tool to synthesize available literature, clarify key findings, and identify knowledge gaps on this emerging topic.[13] The review was reported according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systemic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) approach.[14]

Data sources and searches

We conducted a systematic search of the literature to identify studies on parental feeding practices in the context of FI both prior to, and during, the COVID-19 pandemic. The search strategy was developed by health sciences librarians (HR, CH, JB) with feedback from the review team. We searched MEDLINE via PubMed, EMBASE via Elsevier, PsycINFO via EBSCO, Cochrane Central via OVID, and Scopus via Elsevier up to April 21, 2023. A combination of database-specific terms and keywords related to parental feeding and FI were used. The full search strategy is available at <http://hdl.handle.net/10342/12485>. Articles were uploaded to Covidence, a web-based tool to facilitate the production of systematic reviews.¹⁵ This review protocol was registered on Open Sciences Framework (<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/AGHKU>).

Eligibility criteria

Eligible studies included English language, peer-reviewed articles, published after January 1st, 2012 that met the following inclusion criteria: (1) households in the U.S. with children under the age of 18 (2) screened for FI using a validated survey (3) the association with parental feeding practices was assessed using a validated survey tool (defined as those that have been tested to ensure reliability and accuracy). Studies were excluded if (1) they were published outside the U.S. (2) children were over 18 years old (3) parents did not live in the same household as the child(ren) (4) did not evaluate households for FI (5) FI or parental feeding practices were evaluated using a non-validated survey tool.

Study selection

All abstracts/study titles were independently reviewed by two investigators for eligibility. Conflicts were resolved by a third reviewer (JGW). The full text of eligible studies, or if eligibility was uncertain, was reviewed independently by two investigators (JGW and CJO) and conflicts were resolved through discussion.

Data extraction and analysis

Our data extraction form was pilot tested and revised. Two investigators (CJO and SR) independently extracted data from included studies for information about author, publication year, study timeframe (pre-COVID-19/during COVID-19), study location, recruitment source, sample size, child demographics (age, sex, weight measurement), parent demographics (caregiver type, race/ethnicity), degree of household FI in the study population, FI and parental feeding practices survey tools, and key findings related to the association between FI and parental feeding practices. Extracted data was independently reviewed by a third investigator (JGW) for accuracy and completeness. One investigator (JGW) independently synthesized data using a descriptive format.

Results

Pre-COVID-19 Studies

Study Characteristics

Our database searches identified 11,916 abstracts. Seventeen articles met all inclusion criteria (Figure 1). Most (n = 11) studies took place prior to the start of the COVID-19 pandemic [7,16–25] (hereinafter defined as March 11, 2020). [26] Of these studies, six (54.5%) recruited participants from one of the following government assistance programs: WIC (Special Supplemental Nutrition Program for Women, Infants and Children), SNAP (Supplemental Nutrition Assistance Program) or Head Start preschool program. [7,16–19,22] Three (27.3%) studies recruited from primary care clinics, [7,20,21] one (9.1%) used a crowdsourcing website, [23] and one (9.1%) recruited from a metropolis middle/high school. [25] The study population average age ranged 2.3 months [20] to middle and high school age adolescents. [7,17,20,21,24] Mothers represented all or most of the parental study population. Studies varied in parental race or ethnicity. The majority of parents identified as Hispanic/Latino in five (45.5%) studies, [7,17,20,21,24] White (n=3, 27.3%), [18,22,23] and African American (n=2, 18.2%) (Table 1). [16,19]

Figure 1: PRISMA-ScR Flow Diagram

The Association Between FI and Feeding Practices of Pre-COVID-19 Studies

The association between FI and parental feeding practices varied. FI was significantly associated with parental feeding practices in nine (82%) studies.[7,16,17,19–21,23–25] FI was most often associated with controlling feeding practices, including pressured (45.5%)[7,16,20,21,23,24] and restrictive (36.4%)[7,19,23,25] feeding practices. Armstrong et. al, found that the association between FI and restrictive eating was mediated by a mother’s personal restrained eating.[19] Indulgent and laissez-faire parental feeding practices, decreased infant self-feeding,[24] and obesogenic practices (immediately feeding a baby when they cry)[21] were also associated with FI. Three (27.3%) studies[16–18] found no association with restrictive feeding and two (18.2%)[16,18] found no association with monitoring feeding practices; one study found no association with feeding practices characterized as authoritarian, indulgent, and uninvolved.[22] Additionally, while not all studies evaluated parental concern about a child’s weight, four studies found parents in FI households were more likely to be concerned about their child’s weight,[7,16,21,25] specifically overweight (n =3).[7,16,21]

Studies During COVID-19

Study Characteristics

Six studies (35.3%) took place during the COVID-19 pandemic.[32–37] Three (50%) published by Adams et al. used social media to recruit a national sample.[32–34] Elgersma and colleagues used two randomized controlled trials to obtain a rural and urban sample from Minnesota,[35] and two (33.3%) recruited participants from government assistance programs (WIC and SNAP36 and public health department classes).[37] The study population of included studies ranged from newborn [37] to 9.6 years. [32] Mothers made up all or most of the parental study population. Most (83%) studies were characterized by parents that mostly identified as White, [32–35,37] except one study (16.7%) which consisted of parents that mostly identified as Hispanic/Latino. [36]

Food Insecurity and Feeding Practice Measures

The 6-item USDA Household Food Security Module was used in most studies (83%) except one (16.7%),[32–35,37] which used the 2-item version. [36] The proportion of participants experiencing FI ranged from 18% [35] to 48%. [37] Similar to pre-COVID-19 studies, most used the CFQ (66.7%). [27] The remaining two studies used surveys not used by any of the pre-COVID-19 studies, the Food Parenting Inventory (FPI) [36,38] and the Children’s Eating Behavior Questionnaire (CEBQ). [36,39]

The Association Between Food Insecurity and Feeding Practices During COVID-19

Of the six studies that occurred during the pandemic, four (66.7%) found no association between FI and restrictive [32,34–36] or monitoring [32–34,36] feeding practices. Three (50%) studies during the pandemic had study timelines that overlapped with the start of the pandemic. [35–37] Eagleton et al., evaluated low-income mothers’ feeding practices in 2-month-old infants and found that prenatal FI was indirectly associated with pressured feeding mediated through parental mental health symptoms (anxiety/depression); however, there was no direct association between food security status and feeding practices. [35] Two studies (33.3%) found no association between FI and feeding practices, Elgersma et al. who examined restrictive feeding [35] and McCurdy et al. who examined several feeding practices (encouraging trying new foods, mealtime structure, pressure to eat, restriction of food, food as a reward, monitoring, and responsive to child fullness cues). [36] For these three studies (Eagleton, Elgersma, and McCurdy) most of the study period occurred prior to the COVID-19 pandemic and may not be entirely reflective of the impacts of the pandemic on FI and parental feeding practices. Additionally, no comparison was made between findings before and after the start of the pandemic.

The other half (n=3) of studies during the pandemic were published by Adams et al. [32–34] These studies followed a national cohort of 333-584, mostly White, mothers recruited through Facebook social media. The Adams et al studies surveyed participants via an online survey at different points during the

pandemic and examined pre/post-pandemic changes using a retrospective self-report of pre-pandemic outcomes. [32–34] These studies observed an increase in parental feeding practices (pressured, restrictive, and monitoring) among households overall. However, the most recently published study found that only pressured feeding, pressuring a child to increase food consumption, remained statistically significantly elevated when measured at timepoint May 2021, compared to pre-pandemic levels, and was higher in FI households. [34] Forty-one percent of studies assessed parental concern about their child’s weight and observed an increase in parental concern about their child being overweight during the pandemic. This concern was sustained when measured in May 2021 and higher among FI households. [34]

Discussion

This scoping review examined the association between household FI and parental feeding practices both prior to, and during, the COVID-19 pandemic. Studies published both prior to, and during, the COVID-19 pandemic had mixed findings. However, several studies in both timeframes demonstrated an association between FI and parental feeding practices. Controlling feeding practices—pressure to eat and restriction of food—were most frequently associated with FI. Although not measured in our included studies, parents with FI are more likely to inaccurately perceive their healthy weight child as being underweight. This may lead to a pressured parental feeding practice which pressures a child to eat more and increase their food consumption. [40] On the other hand, under resource-scarce conditions, parents may use restrictive feeding practices to conserve resources thereby limiting the quantity of food a child is offered. [41] Parents may also pressure their children to eat available food due to uncertainty of food access or so that food is not wasted. [42] Interestingly, Adams et al. found an increase in pressured feeding during the pandemic that was sustained a year after the start of the pandemic and higher among FI households. [34] The COVID-19 pandemic created uncertainty in several domains impacting food resources that disproportionately affected low-income households, such as financial stressors, school closures limiting access to supplemental nutrition programs, and limited access to grocery stores that may explain the disproportionate impact the COVID-19 impact had on pressured feeding among FI families. [4,43] FI and its negative health sequelae can be more common in Black and Hispanic communities, as well as communities with fewer economic resources. Understanding the association between FI and parental feeding behaviors in diverse communities will be an important area of research. Especially with research suggesting FI and parental feeding behaviors can vary by race and ethnicity. [20]

In addition to controlling feeding practices, defined as pressured and restrictive feeding, several included studies also evaluated monitoring as a feeding style. Monitoring is defined as parents tracking the quality and quantity of food consumed by their child. Most of the studies we identified, both prior to and during the pandemic, examining monitoring parental feeding practices, found no association with FI. Adams et al. noted an initial increase in monitoring during the COVID-19 pandemic although this change was not sustained. [32–34] The lack of variety of foods in FI households may potentially explain this finding. We also found several studies, both prior to and during the pandemic, that demonstrated greater concern about children becoming overweight in FI households, although this outcome was not part of our inclusion criteria. FI has been associated with overweight and obesity in adults¹ and potentially children. [44,45] Parental concern about their child’s weight and the potential risk for obesity facing children in FI households indicate a need for interventions to improve food access and education on feeding practices.

Conclusion

Our search did not include unpublished studies, otherwise known as a grey literature search. There was significant heterogeneity in feeding practice tools used, which limited comparisons and may also partially explain the mixed findings we observed. The process of feeding is complex and influenced by parent, child, social, and environmental factors. Studies may not have taken into consideration, such as parental stress and depressed mood which has been associated with parental feeding practices. [41,42] There were a limited number of studies published post-pandemic that met inclusion criteria indicating a

need for further research in this area. There were also several differences between studies conducted before versus during the pandemic that limit comparisons.

Pre-pandemic studies mostly recruited from government assistance programs and included parents that mostly identified as Hispanic/Latino, whereas studies overlapping with the pandemic or thereafter consisted of a majority White parental population recruited through Facebook. Notably, an under-representation of ethnic and racial minorities in the studies collected during the pandemic limit evaluation of sociocultural influences on parental feeding.

Additional limitations also include potential for response bias. All 17 studies evaluated as part of this scoping review utilized survey tools to gather participant data. Collected data may be limited by participant response bias, recall bias, and/or Hawthorne bias in which participants may alter behavior given the nature of being observed for study.

Future Directions

Household FI was impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. [46] More than two years after the onset of the pandemic, there is evidence that FI rates have returned to pre-pandemic levels, [34] and other sequelae of the pandemic have abated—such as school closures and unemployment rates. [47] Yet, there is evidence that rates of FI among those with very low food security have persisted above pre-pandemic levels. [34] Future studies should delineate severity of FI in order to adequately capture changes faced by those with very low food security, especially given that very low food security is characterized by disrupted eating practices and reduced food intake. [2] Notably, as limitations noted under-representation by racial and ethnic minorities in post-pandemic surveys, future studies should examine participants of greater diversity. Future studies should also further investigate the potential role of cultural feeding practices as an influence on parental feeding style. Furthermore, most studies to date have examined the association between FI and maladaptive feeding practices, however, future research is needed on protective factors that may buffer stressors facing FI households and support positive parental feeding practices.

Despite some limitations, findings from this scoping review suggest that household FI not only influences the availability of food, but also how parents feed their children. Parents in FI households may be at risk for adverse parent feeding practices, such as pressured and restrictive feeding behaviors. These findings highlight the need to evaluate and address FI, as well as educate providers about parental feeding practices.

Table 1. Studies Examining the Association Between Food Insecurity and Parental Feeding Practices (N=17)

First Author, Date	Study Timeframe	Recruitment Source	Child Details (sample size; age mean (SD) or range; sex; weight measurement)	Caregiver Details (sample size; caregiver type; race/ethnicity)	Degree of FI	FI Tool	Feeding Practice Tool	Key Finding
During COVID-19 (n=6)								
Adams 2022	May 2020 – May 2021 (pre/During COVID-19) *pre-COVID-19 based on retrospective self-report	Social media, national sample	N = 333 9.3 (3.7) years Female (50%)	N = 333 Female (95%) White (85%)	FI increased during COVID-19, back to pre-COVID-19 at 27%. Increase in very low FS sustained at ↑ 7% from pre-COVID-19	6-item USDA Household Food Security Module	CFQ	Pressured feeding in FS/FI households increased during COVID-19 and remained significantly elevated at 5/2021. Pressured feeding differed by food security status, higher in FI households. Changes in restrictive and monitoring feeding were not sustained. Increase in concern for child being overweight was sustained and higher among FI households.
Adams 2021	May-Sept. 2020 (pre/During COVID-19) *pre-COVID-19 based on retrospective self-report	Social media	N=433 9.4 (3.8) years Male (51%) Overweight/obese (27%)	N=433 Female (95%) White (85%) African American (6.7%) Asian (3.9%)	37% pre-COVID-19, post-COVID-19: 54% May 2020, 45% Sept. 2020	6-item USDA Household Food Security Module	CFQ	Restrictive and pressured feeding increased for some FI and FS families during COVID-19 but returned to pre-COVID-19 levels by 9/2020. Concern about child being overweight increased during COVID-19 and was sustained for FI parents only.

Adams 2020	Apr. – May 2020 (Pre/During COVID-19) *pre-COVID-19 based on retrospective self-report	Social media, national sample	N=584 9.6 (3.8) years Female (52%) Overweight/obese (26%)	N=584 Female (95%) White (83%) Hispanic/Latino (15%) African American (6%) Asian (4%) American Indian (7%)	Pre- vs during COVID-19: FS ↓17%, Very low FS ↑ 20%	6-item USDA Household Food Security Module	CFQ	Pressured, restrictive, and monitoring increased during COVID-19. Only pressured feeding increased significantly more among FI parents. Concern about child being overweight increased during COVID-19, with a greater increase for FI parents.
Elgersma 2023	HOME Plus (2010-2016) NU-HOME (2016-2022) (Pre/During COVID-19)	HOME Plus and NU-HOME RCTs or rural and urban MN	N=264 9.2 (1.5) years Female (52%) BMI: FI 1.18 (SD 0.96), FS 0.89 (SD 0.83)	N=264 62% White (FI), 83% White (FS)	18% FI	6-item USDA Household Food Security Module	CFQ	FI not associated with restrictive feeding.
Eagleton 2022	Feb. 2019 – Oct. 2020 (pre/During COVID-19)	iGROW study, Guilford County, NC, public health department classes, SNAP, WIC, OB/Gyn clinics, social media	N=170 39 weeks average gestational age Female (50%)	N=170 Mothers (100%) White (51%) African American (34%) Hispanic/Latino (8%) Mixed race/other (14%)	48% prenatal FI	6-item USDA Household Food Security Module	IFSQ at 2 months of age	Prenatal FI not directly associated with pressured feeding, yet indirectly associated when mediated through parental mental health symptoms.

McCurdy 2022	Jul. 2019- Jul. 2020 (pre/During COVID-19)	WIC clinics	N=66 43.5 (10.6) months Male (55%) BMI .685 (SD 1.1)	N=66 Mothers (91%) Hispanic/Latino (87%)	45% FI	2-item USDA Household Food Security Module	FPI, CEBQ	FI not significantly associated with parental feeding practices.
Pre-COVID-19 (n=11)								
Lappan 2022	2017-2019 (recruitment)	Social services (WIC, sliding scale medical offices, women's shelters)	3-8 years BMI 94% (SD 5.3)	N = 103 Single Mothers (100%) African American (41%) White (31%) Hispanic/Latino (13%) Mixed race (12%) American Indian/Alaskan Native (4%)	61% FI	18-item USDA Household Food Security Module	CFQ	Maternal history of FI during childhood and current FI significantly associated with pressured feeding practices and concern about child being overweight, no significant associated with monitoring or restrictive feeding.

Foster 2022	2017-2019	Head Start in Oregon (Growing Healthy Together study); San Antonio, TX safety-net provider	<p>Oregon study: N = 168 2-5 years Female (46%) BMI: FI 98% (SD 4), FI 97% (SD 5)</p> <p>Texas study: N = 48 2-5 years Female (~50%) BMI: FI 92% (SD 13), FS 93% (SD 10)</p>	<p>Hispanic/Latino (100%)</p> <p>Oregon study: N = 168</p> <p>Texas study: N = 48</p>	<p>Oregon study: 39%</p> <p>Texas study: 21%</p>	6-item USDA Household Food Security Module	CFPQ	FS significantly associated with higher monitoring practices, and no association with controlling practices.
Na 2021	May 2017-May 2018	Head Start preschools	<p>N=304</p> <p>Parent (90%) Female (95%) White (94%)</p>	<p>N=304</p> <p>Parent (90%) Female (95%) White (94%)</p>	38% FI	8-item USDA Household Food Security Module	CFPQ	FI not significantly associated with parental feeding practices.
Armstrong 2020	2007-2010 *6- & 12-month follow-up	WIC/SNAP eligible	<p>N=277</p> <p>20 (5.5) months Male (53%) BMI 0.54 (SD 1.13)</p>	<p>N=277</p> <p>All mothers African American (70%) White (28%)</p>	40% FS	6-item USDA Household Food Security Module	TFBQ	Mothers' personal retrained eating mediated the association between FI and child restrictive & response feeding.

Orr 2020	2010 - 2017	Resident primary care clinics	N = 503 25 (1.3) months Male (49%) Female (51%)	N = 503 Hispanic/Latino (52%) African American (29%) White (15%)	37% FI	2-item USDA Household Food Security Module	CFQ	FI associated with more pressured feeding and greater concern about child becoming overweight.
Orr 2019	2010 - 2017	Resident primary care clinics	N = 842 2.3 (0.4) months Female (51%)	N = 842 Mothers (96%) Fathers (4%) Hispanic/Latino (50%) African American (28%) White (18%)	43% FI	2-item USDA Household Food Security Module	IFSQ	Differences in feeding practices by FI status. FI associated with increased odds of agreeing with obesogenic practices (e.g., immediately feeding a baby when they cry).
Foster 2019		WIC, SNAP, and/or Head Start eligible mother/father /child triads	N=52 3-5 years Mean 4.1 (5.1) years Male (60%) Female (40%) BMI 0.38 (SD 0.97)	N=52 mothers, 52 fathers Mothers: White (40%), Hispanic/Latina (27%), African American (23%), Asian (6%) Fathers: White (62%), Hispanic/Latino (33%), African American (14%), Asian (6%)	8% low/very low FS * avg of mothers/ fathers	18-item USDA Household Food Security Module	CFSQ	FI not significantly associated with parental feeding practices. FI significantly associated with lower child BMI.

Darling 2018	Amazon Mechanical Turk crowdsourcing website	N=790 7-17 years Mean 11 Female (48%) Overweight/obese (42%)	N=790 Mothers (65%) White (79%) African American (12%) Asian (4%) American Indian (2%)	42% FI	18-item USDA Household Food Security Module	CFQ	Greater levels of FI significantly associated with more restrictive and pressured feeding practices.
Gross 2018	Large urban hospital prenatal and pediatric clinics	N=412	N=412 All mothers All Hispanic/Latina	32% FI during pregnancy 19% FI at 10 months	18-item USDA Household Food Security Module	IFSQ	FI associated with pressuring, indulgent, and laissez-faire feeding and less infant self-feeding.
Bauer 2015	Minneapolis/St Paul MN schools	N=2,087 Adolescents	N=2,087 All mothers	40% FI	6-item USDA Household Food Security Module	CFQ	Very low FI significantly associated with restrictive feeding practices and greater concern about sons' weight.
Gross 2012	NYC WIC center	N=201 2 weeks - 6 months Mean 3 months (1.95) Male (54%) Overweight (7%)	N=201 All mothers Hispanic/Latino (84%)	35% FI	18-item USDA Household Food Security Module	CFQ	FI associated with more restrictive and pressured feeding. FI associated with greater concern about child becoming overweight.

References

1. Coleman-Jensen A, Rabbitt M, Gregory C, Singh A. Statistical Supplement to Household Food Security in the United States in 2020.; 2023. Accessed June 15, 2023. <https://www.ers.usda.gov/webdocs/publications/102072/ap-091.pdf?v=462>
2. Definitions of Food Security. U.S. Department of Agriculture, Economic Research Service; 2022. Accessed June 15, 2023. <https://www.ers.usda.gov/topics/food-nutrition-assistance/food-security-in-the-u-s/definitions-of-food-security/#:~:text=Food%20insecurity%E2%80%94the%20condition%20assessed,may%20result%20from%20food%20insecurity.>
3. Wolfson JA, Leung CW. Food Insecurity and COVID-19: Disparities in Early Effects for US Adults. *Nutrients*. 2020;12(6):1648. doi:10.3390/nu12061648
4. Tester JM, Rosas LG, Leung CW. Food Insecurity and Pediatric Obesity: a Double Whammy in the Era of COVID-19. *Curr Obes Rep*. 2020;9(4):442-450. doi:10.1007/s13679-020-00413-x
5. Taye FA, Lambert LA, Aryeetey R, Xu B, Brewer G. Anthropometric characteristics of children living in food-insecure households in the USA. *Public Health Nutr*. 2021;24(15):4803-4811. doi:10.1017/S1368980021002378
6. Liu J, Rehm CD, Onopa J, Mozaffarian D. Trends in Diet Quality Among Youth in the United States, 1999-2016. *JAMA*. 2020;323(12):1161. doi:10.1001/jama.2020.0878
7. Gross RS, Mendelsohn AL, Fierman AH, Racine AD, Messito MJ. Food Insecurity and Obesogenic Maternal Infant Feeding Styles and Practices in Low-Income Families. *Pediatrics*. 2012;130(2):254-261. doi:10.1542/peds.2011-3588
8. Kaur J, Lamb MM, Ogden CL. The Association between Food Insecurity and Obesity in Children—The National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey. *J Acad Nutr Diet*. 2015;115(5):751-758. doi:10.1016/j.jand.2015.01.003
9. Hurley KM, Cross MB, Hughes SO. A Systematic Review of Responsive Feeding and Child Obesity in High-Income Countries. *J Nutr*. 2011;141(3):495-501. doi:10.3945/jn.110.130047
10. Vaughn AE, Ward DS, Fisher JO, et al. Fundamental constructs in food parenting practices: a content map to guide future research. *Nutr Rev*. 2016;74(2):98-117. doi:10.1093/nutrit/nuv061
11. Johnson SL, Birch LL. Parents' and children's adiposity and eating style. *Pediatrics*. 1994;94(5):653-661.
12. Abrams SA, Avalos A, Gray M, Hawthorne KM. High Level of Food Insecurity among Families with Children Seeking Routine Care at Federally Qualified Health Centers during the Coronavirus Disease 2019 Pandemic. *J Pediatr X*. 2020;4:100044. doi:10.1016/j.ympdx.2020.100044
13. Munn Z, Peters MDJ, Stern C, Tufanaru C, McArthur A, Aromataris E. Systematic review or scoping review? Guidance for authors when choosing between a systematic or scoping review approach. *BMC Med Res Methodol*. 2018;18(1):143. doi:10.1186/s12874-018-0611-x
14. Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, et al. PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and Explanation. *Ann Intern Med*. 2018;169(7):467-473. doi:10.7326/M18-0850
15. Covidence. www.covidence.org
16. Lappan SN, Harman T, Pavela G, Hendricks P. Relationship Between Food Security Status in a Caregiver's Family of Origin and Current Feeding Practices Among Low-Income, Single, Female Primary Caregivers. *Fam Community Health*. 2022;45(4):257-266. doi:10.1097/FCH.0000000000000347
17. Foster BA, Linville D, Miller-Bedell ER, Mahjoub H. Food security and feeding behaviours in low-income, Latinx families with preschool-aged children. *Public Health Nutr*. 2022;25(12):3306-3311. doi:10.1017/S1368980022001884
18. Na M, Jomaa L, Eagleton SG, Savage JS. Head Start Parents With or Without Food Insecurity and With Lower Food Resource Management Skills Use Less Positive Feeding Practices in Preschool-Age Children. *J Nutr*. 2021;151(5):1294-1301. doi:10.1093/jn/nxab001
19. Armstrong B, Hepworth AD, Black MM. Hunger in the household: Food insecurity and associations with maternal eating and toddler feeding. *Pediatr Obes*. 2020;15(10). doi:10.1111/ijpo.12637
20. Orr CJ, Ben-Davies M, Ravanbakht SN, et al. Parental Feeding Beliefs and Practices and Household Food Insecurity in Infancy. *Acad Pediatr*. 2019;19(1):80-89. doi:10.1016/j.acap.2018.09.007
21. Orr CJ, Ravanbakht S, Flower KB, et al. Associations Between Food Insecurity and Parental Feeding Behaviors of Toddlers. *Acad Pediatr*. 2020;20(8):1163-1169. doi:10.1016/j.acap.2020.05.020
22. Foster JS, Adamsons K, Vollmer RL, Mobley AR. A pilot study of low-income mothers and fathers of preschool age children to determine the relationship of food security and nutrition assistance on feeding style and child body weight. *J Hunger Environ Nutr*. 2019;14(5):698-708. doi:10.1080/19320248.2018.1491363

23. Darling KE, Fahrenkamp AJ, Ruzicka EB, Sato AF. Controlling feeding practices mediate the association between food insecurity and parent-reported child BMI percentile. *Child Health Care*. 2018;47(3):275-288. doi:10.1080/02739615.2017.1337517
24. Gross RS, Mendelsohn AL, Messito MJ. Additive effects of household food insecurity during pregnancy and infancy on maternal infant feeding styles and practices. *Appetite*. 2018;130:20-28. doi:10.1016/j.appet.2018.07.016
25. Bauer KW, MacLehose R, Loth KA, Fisher JO, Larson NI, Neumark-Sztainer D. Eating- and Weight-Related Parenting of Adolescents in the Context of Food Insecurity. *J Acad Nutr Diet*. 2015;115(9):1408-1416. doi:10.1016/j.jand.2015.01.011
26. CDC Museum COVID-19 Timeline. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention; 2023. Accessed April 1, 2023. <https://www.cdc.gov/museum/timeline/covid19.html#Early-2020>
27. Birch LL, Fisher JO, Grimm-Thomas K, Markey CN, Sawyer R, Johnson SL. Confirmatory factor analysis of the Child Feeding Questionnaire: a measure of parental attitudes, beliefs and practices about child feeding and obesity proneness. *Appetite*. 2001;36(3):201-210. doi:10.1006/appe.2001.0398
28. Thompson AL, Mendez MA, Borja JB, Adair LS, Zimmer CR, Bentley ME. Development and validation of the Infant Feeding Style Questionnaire. *Appetite*. 2009;53(2):210-221. doi:10.1016/j.appet.2009.06.010
29. Musher-Eizenman D, Holub S. Comprehensive Feeding Practices Questionnaire: Validation of a New Measure of Parental Feeding Practices. *J Pediatr Psychol*. 2007;32(8):960-972. doi:10.1093/jpepsy/jsm037
30. Hughes SO, Power TG, Orlet Fisher J, Mueller S, Nicklas TA. Revisiting a neglected construct: parenting styles in a child-feeding context. *Appetite*. 2005;44(1):83-92. doi:10.1016/j.appet.2004.08.007
31. Kristen M. H, M. Reese P, Margo C, et al. Systematic Development and Validation of a Theory-Based Questionnaire to Assess Toddler Feeding. *J Nutr*. 2013;143(12):2044-2049. doi:10.3945/jn.113.179846
32. Adams EL, Caccavale LJ, Smith D, Bean MK. Food Insecurity, the Home Food Environment, and Parent Feeding Practices in the Era of COVID-19. *Obesity*. 2020;28(11):2056-2063. doi:10.1002/oby.22996
33. Adams EL, Caccavale LJ, Smith D, Bean MK. Longitudinal patterns of food insecurity, the home food environment, and parent feeding practices during COVID-19. *Obes Sci Pract*. 2021;7(4):415-424. doi:10.1002/osp4.499
34. Adams EL, Caccavale LJ, Smith DI, Bean MK. Food Insecurity, Federal Nutrition Support, and Parent Feeding Practices During COVID-19: A 1-Year Follow-up Study. *Public Health Rep*. 2023;138(2):323-332. doi:10.1177/00333549221132532
35. Elgersma KM, Martin CL, Friend S, Lee J, Horning ML, Fulkerson JA. Food Insecurity and Parent Feeding Practices in Urban and Rural Children Aged 7–12 Years. *J Nutr Educ Behav*. 2023;55(2):105-113. doi:10.1016/j.jneb.2022.08.014
36. McCurdy K, Gans KM, Risica PM, Fox K, Tovar A. Food insecurity, food parenting practices, and child eating behaviors among low-income Hispanic families of young children. *Appetite*. 2022;169:105857. doi:10.1016/j.appet.2021.105857
37. Eagleton SG, Shriver LH, Buehler C, Wideman L, Leerkes EM. Longitudinal Associations Among Food Insecurity During Pregnancy, Parental Mental Health Symptoms, Controlling Feeding Styles, and Infant Food Responsiveness. *J Nutr*. 2022;152(12):2659-2668. doi:10.1093/jn/nxacc225
38. Power TG, Johnson SL, Beck AD, Martinez AD, Hughes SO. The Food Parenting Inventory: Factor structure, reliability, and validity in a low-income, Latina sample. *Appetite*. 2019;134:111-119. doi:10.1016/j.appet.2018.11.033
39. Wardle J, Guthrie CA, Sanderson S, Rapoport L. Development of the Children's Eating Behaviour Questionnaire. *J Child Psychol Psychiatry*. 2001;42(7):963-970. doi:10.1111/1469-7610.00792
40. Dovico JM, Palmer RJ, Perrin EM, Brown CL. Food Insecurity Associated With Underestimation of Weight Status in Children With a Healthy Weight. *Acad Pediatr*. 2020;20(2):188-192. doi:10.1016/j.acap.2019.04.009
41. Berger AT, Widome R, Erickson DJ, Laska MN, Harnack LJ. Changes in association between school foods and child and adolescent dietary quality during implementation of the Healthy, Hunger-Free Kids Act of 2010. *Ann Epidemiol*. 2020;47:30-36. doi:10.1016/j.annepidem.2020.05.013
42. Arlinghaus KR, Laska MN. Parent Feeding Practices in the Context of Food Insecurity. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2021;18(2):366. doi:10.3390/ijerph18020366
43. Niles MT, Bertmann F, Belarmino EH, Wentworth T, Biehl E, Neff R. The Early Food Insecurity Impacts of COVID-19. *Nutrients*. 2020;12(7):2096. doi:10.3390/nu12072096
44. St. Pierre C, Ver Ploeg M, Dietz WH, et al. Food Insecurity and Childhood Obesity: A Systematic Review. *Pediatrics*. 2022;150(1):e2021055571. doi:10.1542/peds.2021-055571
45. Pan L, Sherry B, Njai R, Blanck HM. Food Insecurity Is Associated with Obesity among US Adults in 12 States. *J Acad Nutr Diet*. 2012;112(9):1403-1409. doi:10.1016/j.jand.2012.06.011

46. Kim-Mozeleski JE, Pike Moore SN, Trapl ES, Perzynski AT, Tsoh JY, Gunzler DD. Food Insecurity Trajectories in the US During the First Year of the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Prev Chronic Dis.* 2023;20:220212. doi:10.5888/pcd20.220212

47. The Employment Situation - May 2023. U.S. Department of Labor Bureau of Labor Statistics; 2023. Accessed June 20, 2023. <https://www.bls.gov/news.release/pdf/empst.pdf>

Legal Considerations in Informed Consent: Disclosing Statistical Mortality Information to Late-Stage Cancer Patients

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Abstract

Physicians have a duty to ensure informed consent is achieved to respect patient autonomy but guidelines about the specific details required for informed consent remain situational, nebulous, and may vary by jurisdiction. In addition to the harm to patients, failures in informed consent can carry severe legal consequences for physicians. This commentary examines the legal considerations surrounding the disclosure of statistical mortality information to late-stage cancer patients within the context of informed consent in contemporary medical practice. Beginning with an exploration of the evolution of informed consent following *Canterbury v Spence*, this discussion underscores the transition from a professional-centered to a patient-centered approach. Surveys of medical oncologists indicate large variation in practice standards of communicating prognostic information, and most oncologists believed formal training in this communication is both necessary and yet was insufficient in their education. While accurate and precise prognostic information holds undeniable utility for patients, patient understanding of prognostic medical information is subject to numerous biases and may be further complicated by levels of statistical literacy. The precedent set in *Arato v Avedon* ruled that statistical mortality information is not always required for informed consent, but this analysis highlights certain situations in which disclosure of such information by physicians may be legally required. These situations may become more prevalent as medical science advances, and this commentary provides informed consent guidelines that uphold legal obligations for medical practitioners, to facilitate shared patient-physician understanding.

Introduction

The doctrine of informed consent in medicine has deep historical roots, stemming from the post-World War II Nuremberg Code, which was crafted to prevent the exploitation of individuals in unethical medical experiments. This doctrine is grounded in the fundamental principle that individuals have the right to decide what medical procedures may be performed on their bodies, [1] a corollary of the right to bodily autonomy. Violations of this right thus expose physicians to potential medical malpractice litigation and professional consequences. While informed consent dictates that physicians must provide patients with sufficient information to make informed decisions about their healthcare, strict definitions of the type and quantity of information disclosed are not present in applicable law. This article explores the nuances of informed consent, with a particular focus on the extent to which physicians are required to disclose statistical mortality information to late-stage cancer patients. This analysis aims to guide physicians in navigating the delicate balance between patient autonomy and professional standards when disclosing information to ensure that patients can make well-informed choices regarding their medical care.

Informed Consent before *Canterbury v Spence*

Prior to the 1970s, U.S. judicial courts held that a physician's duty to provide information was dictated by the standard of care. [2] This standard was heavily dependent upon the setting of informed consent, for standards of care are different across hospitals of disparate resources, between medical specialties, and for distinct cultures of care within communities. Accordingly, determination of this standard in court was reliant upon expert testimony. This system heavily favored physicians in medical malpractice cases, as physicians were wary of testifying against colleagues. In addition, this system provided limited legal recourse for inadequate information disclosures, provided the level of disclosure was not dissimilar to that of other physicians in similar clinical settings.

In 1972, *Canterbury v Spence* instituted a paradigm shift in medical informed consent. [3] Rather than relying on the professional standard of care, the *Canterbury* case ruled that informed consent required disclosure of information that would be important to a reasonable person. [3] This relies less on expert testimony, and rather invites the jury to imagine whether a reasonable patient in the community would consider the information material to medical decisions. [3] In practice, this shift often meant physicians were required to disclose more information to facilitate informed consent, and since 1972, additional cases have debated the precise details that are necessary to disclose to a reasonable patient. [4–6] Currently, states are divided in their use of the traditional professional standard for disclosure versus the patient-centered standard pioneered in the *Canterbury* case; the latter is discussed below.

Canterbury v Spence: the landmark case in informed consent

Jerry Canterbury was a 19-year-old clerk who presented to clinic with severe back pain. [3] At the advice of his neurosurgeon, Dr. William T. Spence, Canterbury underwent a laminectomy in 1958. [3] Unbeknownst to Canterbury, laminectomies have approximately a one percent chance of causing paralysis. [3] After the surgery and a subsequent fall in the hospital, Canterbury was left paralyzed below the waist and incontinent. [3]

Canterbury sued on the grounds of negligence, alleging that he had not been adequately informed of the risks associated with the procedure. [3] The pivotal legal aspect of this case emerged during the 1968 trial when the defense argued that Canterbury's lack of expert testimony should prevent the case from proceeding. [3] However, Judge Spottswood W. Robinson III of the DC Circuit Court allowed the case to go to a jury, establishing a standard for informed consent based on what a reasonable patient would want to know, rendering expert testimony unnecessary. [3]

While the jury ultimately ruled against Canterbury, this case instituted a shift from the professional practice standard. [3] The *Canterbury* case ruled that a reasonable person would want to know, and hence physicians should be required to disclose, the following information: 1) the diagnosis,

2) a description of the nature and purpose of the proposed treatment, 3) the anticipated results of the treatment, and any serious risks or complications, and 4) the nature and risks of treatment alternatives or refusal. [3] This list notably does not explicitly include statistical mortality information – the subject of this commentary – but such information could arguably be required under points 3) and 4). Namely, the proposed treatment may be anticipated to result in a more favorable mortality prognosis than other treatments or withholding treatment, while complications may result in an increased mortality rate. These four guidelines have also been supported in subsequent medical malpractice cases, such as *Nixdorf v Hicken* and *Truman v Thomas*, [4,5] and additional guidelines have been identified in cases such as *Gates v Jenson*, which ruled that physicians are required to disclose personal interests that may influence their judgment. [6] Case law has also identified disclosures that are not required for informed consent, such as risks that are common knowledge, risks that the patient already knows, or other information that would not affect the patient’s medical decisions. [7] Notably, the Canterbury standard for informed consent is personalized in two ways: 1) if the patient is already knowledgeable about the treatment, then they demand fewer disclosures, and 2) a physician must additionally explain unique information such as benefits or risks that may be significant to a particular patient.

Exemptions to the *Canterbury* standard for informed consent exist in medical emergencies, and when information disclosure is likely to cause significant emotional harm to a patient. [8] The latter consideration may be relevant to the disclosure of mortality information to cancer patients, as such information could be damaging to a patient’s psychological health. [9] However, likely due to the innate challenges in evaluating the probability and extent of significant psychological distress following potential information disclosure, such an exemption is transient and hence more relevant to the acute management of diseases, and less relevant to the discussions of long-term care and prognosis that often occur in cancer management. In the absence of these exceptions, the utility of statistical mortality information to late-stage cancer patients must be examined in order to evaluate its legal implications under the *Canterbury standard*.

The utility of statistical mortality information in informed consent

The disclosure of statistical mortality information to cancer patients is debatable between medical oncologists. In a survey of over one thousand physicians, while 98% said that they will tell patients that their condition is terminal, oncologists are divided in either always disclosing prognostic information, or only doing so if their patient indicates their desire for a more quantitative prognosis. [9] In addition, 73% of responders indicated prognosis communication education was inadequate during their training, despite almost all responders believing it should be part of oncologist training. [9] This status quo raises potential issues for states which follow professional standards for disclosures in informed consent, as a single professional standard is lacking, hindering a clear resolution. Patient preferences in the level of quantitative detail delivered during the communication of their prognosis may also vary, which limits the “reasonable person” standard initiated by the *Canterbury* case.

Importantly, informed consent requires not just the mere disclosure of medical information by physicians, but also information must be presented in a simplified manner that is understandable to patients without a medical background. Patient comprehension varies based on the method of information delivery, [10] and can be improved by novel teaching strategies at the cost of a prolonged informed consent process. [11] Following information disclosures, patients often retain mistaken beliefs about the benefits of procedures, [12] indicating that methods of communication must be improved so as not to waste physician resources and time. Statistical mortality information may be more complex than qualitative information about the benefits of a treatment, and hence may be even more difficult to communicate to patients effectively. For example, oncology therapeutics are often supported by clinical

trial data using early efficacy endpoints, including the objective response rate and progression-free survival, and these endpoints do not always correlate with overall survival. [12] Communicating such nuances to manage patient expectations may present a challenge for providers, particularly in health systems where appointment slots are of fixed duration. Indeed, failures of informed consent arising from patient misconceptions (potentially due to ineffective provider communication) may contribute to disastrous consequences including performing surgery on the wrong patient. [14]

Additional obstacles to informed consent also arise that may be more specific to the disclosure of prognostic mortality information. In the context of late-stage cancer patients, it is often difficult for oncologists to accurately predict a patient's prognosis, making the disclosure of such information infeasible. [15] Moreover, the disclosure of statistical mortality information may not facilitate patient understanding, even when providers are confident of a bleak prognosis. In studies of stage IV cancer patients who were told a prognosis of one year or less, patients exhibited optimism bias, illusion of superiority, and other biases exacerbated by higher levels of hope assessed using the Health Hope Index. [16,17] More hopeful patients reported estimated survival of over 4 years longer than less hopeful patients and were more likely to mistakenly believe their treatment was curative rather than palliative. [16,17] Data are mixed regarding whether increased hope affects patient survival, but increased hope is linked to greater rates of healthcare utilization, potentially indicating overtreatment. [16,17]

Set in a status quo where physicians may neglect to mention serious risks associated with medical procedures, the patient-centered standard initiated in the Canterbury case aimed primarily for the disclosure of the existence of risks. [3] The disclosure of prognostic benefits, such as life expectancy, associated with distinct courses of treatment was a secondary goal, and the Canterbury case makes no explicit argument for or against providing quantitative estimates of the incidence of adverse outcomes. [3] While this omission could have been a strategic decision by the plaintiff's attorney, it also suggests that the court did not believe quantitative information was sufficiently salient to be material to the decisions of the "reasonable patient." [3] Patient preferences and understanding may vary based on patient factors such as education and emotional state, as well as the level of certainty associated with the information. Indeed, while one could argue that many Americans would have sufficient statistical literacy to understand point estimates of life expectancy, far fewer patients (and potentially physicians) would understand the confidence interval or credible interval that articulate the level of variance associated with the estimate – an integral characteristic of the estimate. For example, a patient may evaluate a hypothetical treatment that is guaranteed to extend their life by one year differently versus a more variable treatment that has a 50% chance of extending their life by four years and a 50% chance of shortening their life by two years. Both hypothetical treatments produce a mean increase in life expectancy by one year, and yet may be drastically different in outcome, emphasizing the importance of understanding the variance of estimates for making medical decisions. Despite these challenges, however, the utility of a shared patient-provider understanding of low-variance prognostic information is undeniable; a precise understanding of prognosis would provide a reliable timeline for patients to get their affairs in order, which may include organizing finances and custody arrangements for their children. While the barriers to reaching such an understanding have been described above, these barriers do not absolve modern physicians of the ethical responsibility to facilitate patient autonomy, [18] potentially by educating patients on statistical literacy, or by using qualitative terms to indicate risk (e.g., "rarely" or "usually").

The debate surrounding the disclosure of statistical mortality information to cancer patients reflects the complexities and nuances of informed consent, particularly in late-stage cases where

standardized guidelines to ensure effective and ethical patient-physician communication in these challenging situations.

Arato v Avedon: statistical life expectancy is not required for informed consent

The case of *Arato v Avedon* delves into the complex issue of whether physicians should disclose statistical mortality information to cancer patients. [19] Miklos Arato was diagnosed with pancreatic cancer in 1980 and filled out a routine patient questionnaire indicating his desire to be told the truth about his condition. However, Mr. Arato never directly asked his physicians about his prognosis, and his treating physicians did not disclose the high statistical mortality rates associated with pancreatic cancer. While Mr. Arato's physicians recommended a course of chemotherapy and radiation, Mr. Arato eventually succumbed to cancer. Subsequently, Mr. Arato's family filed a lawsuit against his physicians, alleging that they failed to adequately disclose the potential ineffectiveness of the treatment, leading to Mr. Arato's suffering and financial losses.

Mr. Arato's treating physicians cited various reasons for their decision not to disclose specific statistical life expectancy data to their patient. They pointed to Mr. Arato's significant anxiety, suggesting that disclosure of specific prognostic information could have worsened Mr. Arato's psychological health. Additionally, the physicians argued that relying on statistical data alone was not appropriate for informing a patient's prognosis, as it failed to account for the individualized symptoms, medical history, and character traits that could significantly affect the course of the disease. Accordingly, they argued, statistical life expectancy would not be material to a reasonable patient described in the *Canterbury* case. In addition, expert testimony indicated that the standard of practice did not require disclosure of statistical life expectancy. The superior court ruled in favor of the physicians, emphasizing the unreliability of statistical data when applied to individual cases.

Current legal considerations for physicians

Through the examination of the *Canterbury* case, *Arato v Avedon*, and the questionable utility of statistical life expectancy to advanced cancer patients, this analysis concludes that disclosure of statistical mortality information may be legally required when 1) it is common practice for physicians in that setting, in jurisdictions that apply the professional standard for information disclosure, or 2) the physician believes that statistical mortality information is of particular value to the patient, in jurisdictions that abide by the *Canterbury* standard for informed consent. During a lawsuit, jurisdictional considerations determine whether the outcome of such cases will be determined by expert testimony (in the former situation) or by lay jurors (in the latter situation). While the legal standard described in the *Canterbury* case does not necessarily require the disclosure of statistical mortality information, [3] exemplified by *Arato v Avedon*, [19] physicians may still aim to follow ethical guidelines to facilitate patient understanding of prognosis, as an extension of considerations of patient autonomy. [18]

Legally, physicians will be protected so long as they disclose prognostic information to a similar extent to how they were taught or to their colleagues, or when it is indicated that the information is of particular interest based on patient particulars – most evidently, when a patient asks for the prognostic information. In the span of the intricacies of the doctor-patient relationship, these are relatively straightforward guidelines for physicians to follow.

These guidelines may evolve as medical science advances. For example, if physicians were able to predict prognostic outcomes for individual patients to high accuracy, or if statistical literacy increases in patient populations, then this information could become material to a reasonable patient; the *Canterbury* standard may then compel physicians to disclose this information. This would increase the burden on physicians both regarding information disclosures, and regarding the level of required understanding of each of their patients. Effective guidelines on informed consent are required to facilitate effective clinical practice, where the knowledgeable physician must work alongside their patient to aid them in making decisions that facilitate their health and wellbeing.

References

1. Schloendorff v. Society of New York Hospital, 211 N.Y. 125, 105 N.E. 92 (N.Y. 1914).
2. DiFilippo v. Preston, 53 Del. 539, 173 A.2d 333 (Del. 1961).
3. Canterbury v Spence, 464 F.2d 772, 775 (DC Cir 1972).
4. Nixdorf v. Hicken, 612 P.2d 348 (Utah 1980).
5. Truman v Thomas, 27 Cal. 3d 285, 611 P.2d 902 (Cal. 1980).
6. Gates v Jenson, 92 Wash. 2d 246, 595 P.2d 919 (Wash. 1979).
7. Paterick TJ, Carson GV, Allen MC, Paterick TE. Medical Informed Consent: General Considerations for Physicians. *Mayo Clinic Proceedings*. 2008;83(3):313-319. doi:10.4065/83.3.313
8. Cornfeldt v Tongen, 262 N.W.2d 684 (Minn. 1977).
9. Daugherty CK, Hlubocky FJ. What Are Terminally Ill Cancer Patients Told About Their Expected Deaths? A Study of Cancer Physicians' Self-Reports of Prognosis Disclosure. *JCO*. 2008;26(36):5988-5993. doi:10.1200/JCO.2008.17.2221
10. Schenker Y, Meisel A. Informed consent in clinical care: practical considerations in the effort to achieve ethical goals. *JAMA*. 2011;305(11):1130-1131. doi:10.1001/jama.2011.333
11. Fink AS, Prochazka AV, Henderson WG, et al. Enhancement of surgical informed consent by addition of repeat back: a multicenter, randomized controlled clinical trial. *Ann Surg*. 2010;252(1):27-36. doi:10.1097/SLA.0b013e3181e3ec61
12. Merino M, Kasamon Y, Theoret M, Pazdur R, Kluetz P, Gormley N. Irreconcilable Differences: The Divorce Between Response Rates, Progression-Free Survival, and Overall Survival. *JCO*. 2023;41(15):2706-2712. doi:10.1200/JCO.23.00225
13. Rothberg MB, Sivalingam SK, Ashraf J, et al. Patients' and cardiologists' perceptions of the benefits of percutaneous coronary intervention for stable coronary disease. *Ann Intern Med*. 2010;153(5):307-313. doi:10.7326/0003-4819-153-5-201009070-00005
14. Chassin MR, Becher EC. The wrong patient. *Ann Intern Med*. 2002;136(11):826-833. doi:10.7326/0003-4819-136-11-200206040-00012
15. Nahm SH, Martin AJ, Clayton JM, et al. Accuracy of oncologists' estimates of expected survival time in advanced cancer. *JNCI Cancer Spectrum*. 2023;7(6):pkad094. doi:10.1093/jncics/pkad094
16. Chay J, Huynh VA, Cheung YB, et al. The relationship between hope, medical expenditure and survival among advanced cancer patients. *Front Psychol*. 2023;14:1151976. doi:10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1151976
17. Finkelstein EA, Baid D, Cheung YB, et al. Hope, bias and survival expectations of advanced cancer patients: A cross-sectional study. *Psycho-Oncology*. 2021;30(5):780-788. doi:10.1002/pon.5675
18. Beauchamp TL, Childress JF. *Principles of Biomedical Ethics*. 5. ed. Oxford Univ. Press; 2001.
19. Arato v. Avedon, 5 Cal. 4th 1172, 858 P.2d 598 (Cal. 1993).

Legal Considerations of Physicians Practicing Complementary and Alternative Medicine

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Abstract

There is a challenging legal landscape for medical doctors who, in addition to allopathic care, engage in complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) in the United States. While allopathic medicine and CAM have historically independently coexisted, the legal landscape has not adequately addressed the complex issues that physicians face when practicing CAM. Current law does not adequately shield providers from liability, limiting the future development of medicine's engagement with CAM as both relevant medical practices and legal frameworks develop. Considerations of scope of practice for allopathic and CAM providers is critical in assessing what is appropriate to consider medical care. Furthermore, lack of evidence-based practice associated with CAM, giving the field a conceptually experimental quality presents doctors both with opportunities and hindrances to appropriately engaging in CAM. Issues of informed consent and considerations of malpractice within the current American judicial system limit the way that physicians can legally approach CAM in their practice. By analyzing relevant legal precedent, this paper explores the regulation and the liability that allopathic physicians face when incorporating CAM in their clinical encounters.

Introduction

In the United States, allopathic medicine – “a system of medical practice that emphasizes diagnosing and treating disease and the use of conventional, evidence-based therapeutic measures[1] or Western Medicine – has been the foundation of much of modern healthcare.[2] This evidence-based practice is the backbone of the modern medical system and uses a disease-oriented approach to care. In the United States, different elements of medical care are highly regulated, such as medications and medical devices by the FDA,[3] the licensure of physicians by state medical boards,[4] and health-related regulations and laws at the state level.[5] The established supervising system has created an expansive structure for the regulation of what are considered ‘standard’ medical practices with clear frameworks of liability for practicing physicians guided by a variety of entities including national and state-level statutes and regulations, professional practice and clinical guidelines, and licensing boards.[6]

In parallel with common allopathic medical practice, there is a rich history of “complementary and alternative medicine” (CAM) in the United States. CAM, rooted in ancient tradition in contrast to the evidence-based approach of allopathic medicine, generally centers on a whole-body approach and encompasses practices such as acupuncture, herbal medicine, Tai Chi, Reiki, and Ayurveda. CAM practitioners are certified by their own overseeing bodies independent of the allopathic framework.[7] Issues arise in the increasingly murky arena when conventional providers integrate CAM practices into their medical practice. There has been a sharp delineation between Western medicine and CAM. However, CAM is often being used to supplement allopathic medicine and is increasingly embedded in the contemporary healthcare system.[8] When considering the complex issues that physicians face when employing complementary and alternative medicine, the law does not adequately shield providers from liability, limiting the future development of medicine’s engagement with CAM as both relevant medical practices and legal frameworks develop. This paper will explore the regulation of these encounters and the liability that allopathic physicians face when incorporating CAM in their clinical encounters.

Licensing of Complementary and Alternative Medicine in the United States

The use and practice of complementary and alternative medicine in the United States is broad and has many manifestations across disciplines. Independent of the conventional healthcare system, there is an extensive system of CAM providers engaging in a variety of practices such as hypnotism, acupuncture, naturopathy, and Qigong. These providers are licensed and certified by individual state licensing boards but are very restricted in terms of the scope of the care that they are allowed to provide. While allopathic physicians must also abide by state licensing statutes to provide medical care, the scope of practice provided by these statutes is much wider and less restrictive in terms of what medical advice can be given.[8] CAM providers are narrowly restricted in their scope of practice and limited in what “medicine” they can provide.

While licensure varies among states, general principles are consistent and limit CAM providers. *Dent v. West Virginia*, which addressed incorporating botanical approaches into medicine,[9] and *People v. Amber*, which considered the practice of acupuncture by a non-licensed medical provider,[10] have upheld the limitations on CAM providers to treat and diagnose beyond their limited scope of practice.[11] Furthermore, *State of Nebraska, Department of Health v John Hinze*, which concerned the practice of homeopathy and naturopathy without a medical license[12], *North Carolina v F. Belle Howard and J.C. Howard*, which addressed practicing naturopathy under the guise of being a doctor,[13], and *Roget I. Sabastier v State of Florida*, which considered the ramifications of practicing homeopathy with a medical license,[14] all limited the ability of non-allopathic practitioners to consider themselves “doctors;” this limitation was in the public’s best interest to preserve public trust in medical institutions.[15] As licensing boards and regulatory structures determine what care is appropriate and legal, one essential consideration of CAM in the United States is its integration with official allopathic medicine by licensed medical doctors. Questions about whether allopathic doctors must be licensed in CAM to provide,

endorse, or integrate CAM in their practice are critical. Aside from the need for a medical doctor to have CAM-specific licensure to provide such care, it is also necessary to determine whether a physician could uphold a sufficiently high standard of care when engaging in CAM. This standard of care must be consistent with what is expected of them by their training and overseeing medical bodies but also by the public's trust in medical care.

Provision of Complementary and Alternative Medicine

Despite the strict regulations on CAM providers' scope of practice, conventional medical doctors have broad latitude to provide care that they see as appropriate. Texas, for example, has a statute that allows medical doctors to provide CAM without obtaining the relevant CAM licensure, stating, a "licensed physician shall not be found guilty of unprofessional conduct or be found to have committed professional failure to practice medicine in an acceptable manner solely on the basis of employing a health care method of integrative or complementary medicine" provided that the risk of this approach is not greater than an established, evidence-based medical practice.[16] The legislature takes this approach by deeming CAM to be akin to implementing an unproven therapy such as new experimental treatment.[17] While "experimental" tends to imply new, this approach considers experimental treatment to be that which is non-standard due to still lacking a basis in evidence.

This approach is generally broader than other states' approaches, which tend to only require a physician to practice in congruence with what similar physicians would accept or provide as long as "conventional standards of care" have not been violated.[15] A lower standard of care exists for providers who solely work in CAM;[18] accordingly, this puts additional pressure on allopathic providers who employ CAM to demonstrate that their use of CAM is appropriate, safe, and efficacious. A failure to do so has the potential to cause harm, undermine public trust in medical institutions, and expose providers to medical malpractice cases. Furthermore, obtaining informed consent – i.e. ensuring that patients are aware of the risks of the medical intervention or the choice to not undertake a more conventional approach – is critically important to ensure that patients understand the nature of the care that they are receiving and how it may differ from the presumed allopathic, evidence-based treatment that they are expecting.[19]

Patients may seek CAM either from a provider of CAM or an allopathic provider. When a patient seeks out CAM from any provider, informed consent is less likely to be an issue. *Charell v Gonzalez*[20] determined that "patients may insulate their physicians from liability, either partially or wholly, when they assume treatment risks by agreeing to them in a voluntary or informed manner,"[21] including the provision of CAM. In these situations, the crux of the issue is whether it is appropriate for a Western-trained physician who is not trained in CAM to provide CAM; this is a potential issue of malpractice. To avoid malpractice, a physician's care must generally either reflect the standards of what a majority of peer physicians would do or provide care consistent with what a respected minority would do.[15] If there were a respected minority of practitioners who engage in a particular type of CAM, there is theoretically a scenario where doctors can safely and legally provide CAM, per the above standard for avoiding malpractice. This is analogous to the Texas approach that treats CAM as an experimental therapy with few experts in the field attempting new practices. Otherwise, legal precedent suggests that any allopathic doctor, regardless of their training in CAM, is engaging in malpractice through employing CAM in any professional setting that does not meet the criteria for experimental therapy.

However, there are considerable constraints in place before experimental therapy can be adopted. The leading indication for experimental therapy is a situation in which a patient has a condition for which there is currently no adequate other approach. Likewise, many patients become dissatisfied with allopathic medicine that they feel has failed their intractable chronic conditions.[3] Under these circumstances, it is conceivable that a patient could ask a provider for CAM and the doctor must determine whether they will be liable for malpractice if the care goes poorly, and the patient is harmed.

While doctors appear to have latitude to implement CAM – both by the approval of a respected minority and through freedoms to attempt experimental therapies – it still may be inadvisable for a provider to engage in CAM when requested. Although they do not need official licensure to practice CAM, it is reasonable to contend that a physician cannot adequately understand, prescribe, or provide CAM without licensure. Even if the type of CAM theoretically meets professional standards, the physician could potentially be liable if their delivery of the care is below standards given their lack of training. This issue is potentially sidestepped by doctors who obtain CAM licensure, but the mitigation of malpractice risk is theoretically only achieved by those doctors who only use CAM when requested in absence of a satisfactory allopathic alternative. This is clear in cases such as *Schneider v. Revici*, which established that, with an alternative allopathic approach available, an allopathic provider engages in malpractice by providing CAM even at the patient’s request.[20,22] Similarly, *Charell v Gonzalez*, determined that it is not acceptable for a provider to “deviat[e] from “acceptable medical standards”,”[20] which can be understood to include any form of CAM. However, this may not apply when there is not an established or acceptable medical approach to a conventional medical problem, especially when that non-established medical practice is sought by the patient.

The scope of when CAM is appropriate has been well defined for the patient who seeks an alternative to allopathic medicine. *Charell* suggests that physicians who provide CAM have engaged in malpractice, even when the CAM is sought out by the patient. Although *Charell* indicates that a patient could theoretically insulate their provider from liability by requesting CAM, the physician’s requirement not to deviate from acceptable medical standards to avoid malpractice takes priority. *Schneider* limits CAM malpractice to the provision of CAM when an adequate allopathic alternative exists. Critically, however, both cases involved a patient who sought out CAM from their doctor. Based on current precedent, it seems that the most difficult legal cases involving CAM would be when a non-CAM-trained doctor wants to provide CAM – in the absence of an appropriate alternative allopathic treatment - to a patient who has not actively sought it. When patients have conditions for which allopathic medicine doesn’t have a satisfactory intervention, physicians are in uncharted medical territory. Experimental therapies, which are typically grounded in evidence-based, allopathic interventions, are often the first approach. However, a CAM approach could also be considered experimental under the present circumstances. Accordingly, it would not deviate from acceptable practice when provided by an appropriately trained physician. This appears to create a scenario under which an allopathic physician could appropriately provide CAM to a patient.

However, in addition to the malpractice issues discussed above, the matter of informed consent is amplified in this scenario. A doctor suggesting a CAM approach to a CAM-naïve patient is likely unable to rely on the exception carved out by *Charell*: release of the doctor from liability by a patient who assumes all risk on behalf of the physician. A physician requiring a patient to assume all risk for an experimental treatment, even in the face of no alternative treatment modality, seems manipulative by the physician and puts undue pressure on the patient. It seems unlikely that a patient could appropriately and independently consent to an experimental treatment under this condition.

The suggestion of a complementary or alternative medical practice never falls within a physician’s duty of care, but this does not necessarily prohibit a physician from acknowledging CAM.[23] A well-studied, safe, effective alternative medical practice in which the provider is trained, delivered in the absence of acceptable other established therapies, is the narrow window in which an allopathic provider may be able to practice CAM without fear of liability. This is a new area as CAM becomes more mainstream and researched; unsurprisingly, the law has not yet addressed these emerging developments.

Consequences of the Legal Landscape for Complementary and Alternative Medicine

The legal landscape surrounding CAM has created an environment that inhibits the use of CAM in contemporary medicine. The most risk-averse position for physicians to take is never to engage with CAM. This approach eliminates the potential for CAM-related malpractice. However, as CAM practices become more researched and mainstream, there is an increasing legitimacy for physicians (who have been licensed in CAM) to provide this type of care for intractable medical conditions.

Nevertheless, fear of malpractice seems to be a potent deterrent for doctors considering adopting CAM or engaging with CAM-oriented clinical research. The current environment creates a Catch-22 for CAM: CAM practice isn't protected or mainstream so doctors are disincentivized to engage with or research it out of fear of liability; accordingly, because CAM is not researched and protected, it cannot become established and considered an acceptable medical practice. Under the current legal landscape, changes that increase the research around or provision of CAM in the United States are not to be expected. Under these conditions, the author would discourage any provider from engaging in CAM for risk of malpractice cases and violations of informed consent. However, the status quo does not make the extensive history of CAM and patient interest in CAM disappear.

Elsewhere in the world, complementary and alternative medical practice and research is embedded into the healthcare system and legislation. India has a robust history of supporting CAM, both by legally recognizing it as legitimate and by licensing CAM providers at the same level as allopathic doctors.^[24] While a seismic shift in the landscape of CAM in the United States – akin to how India views CAM – is not necessarily indicated, the presence of another established system suggests that the United States' approach to CAM may be too restrictive. The current regulatory environment and liability for physicians stifles much consideration of CAM and will continue to do so moving forward. While it is important to preserve the trust in the healthcare system, which in part derives from an established, evidence-based foundation, there are opportunities for the law to allow physicians to engage in CAM in wider circumstances, provided that they are doing so with appropriately extensive training and that their practice is not at the expense of established allopathic medicine.

References

1. Definition of ALLOPATHIC MEDICINE. Accessed November 11, 2023. <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/allopathic+medicine>
2. Uher I, Cholewa J, Kunicki M, et al. Allopathic and Naturopathic Medicine and Their Objective Consideration of Congruent Pursuit. *Evid Based Complement Alternat Med*. 2020;2020:7525713. doi:10.1155/2020/7525713
3. Research Center for Drug Evaluation and. FDA Related Laws, Regulations, and Guidances. FDA. Published online July 31, 2023. Accessed November 3, 2023. <https://www.fda.gov/drugs/cder-small-business-industry-assistance-sbia/fda-related-laws-regulations-and-guidances>
4. FSMB | Understanding Medical Regulation in the United States. Accessed November 3, 2023. <https://www.fsmb.org/education/understanding-medical-regulation-in-the-united-states/>
5. Division of Health Service Regulation. Accessed November 3, 2023. <https://info.ncdhhs.gov/dhsr/>
6. Vanderpool D. The Standard of Care. *Innov Clin Neurosci*. 2021;18(7-9):50-51.
7. Kisling LA, Stiegmann RA. Alternative Medicine. In: *StatPearls*. StatPearls Publishing; 2023. Accessed November 3, 2023. <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK538520/>
8. Snyder L, ed. *Complementary and Alternative Medicine: Ethics, the Patient, and the Physician*. Humana Press; 2007. doi:10.1007/978-1-59745-381-3
9. *Dent v. West Virginia*, 129 U.S. 114 (1889). Justia Law. Accessed November 11, 2023. <https://supreme.justia.com/cases/federal/us/129/114/>
10. *People v. Amber*, 76 Misc. 2d 267 | Casetext Search + Citor. Accessed November 11, 2023. <https://casetext.com/case/people-v-amber>
11. Cohen MH, Nelson H. Licensure of Complementary and Alternative Practitioners. *AMA Journal of Ethics*. 2011;13(6):374-378. doi:10.1001/virtualmentor.2011.13.6.pfor1-1106
12. *STATE, DEPT. OF HEALTH v. Hinze*. Justia Law. Accessed November 11, 2023. <https://law.justia.com/cases/nebraska/supreme-court/1989/905-7.html>
13. *State v. Howard*. Justia Law. Accessed November 11, 2023. <https://law.justia.com/cases/north-carolina/court-of-appeals/1985/8512sc654-1.html>
14. *Sabastier v. State*, 504 So. 2d 45 | Casetext Search + Citor. Accessed November 11, 2023. <https://casetext.com/case/sabastier-v-state>
15. Weir M. Complementary and Alternative Medicine and Medical Law. In: Beran RG, ed. *Legal and Forensic Medicine*. Springer; 2013:1281-1298. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-32338-6_66
16. *Tex. Admin. Code §§ 200.1-200.3*. Accessed November 3, 2023. <https://www.law.uh.edu/healthlaw/perspectives/MedicalProfessionals/011107ComplRules.html>
17. *Complementary and Integrative Medicine*, Health Law & Policy Institute. Accessed November 3, 2023. <https://www.law.uh.edu/healthlaw/perspectives/MedicalProfessionals/011107Complementary.html>
18. Raposo VL. Complementary and alternative medicine, medical liability and the proper standard of care. *Complementary Therapies in Clinical Practice*. 2019;35:183-188. doi:10.1016/j.ctcp.2019.02.009
19. Ernst E, Cohen MH. Informed Consent in Complementary and Alternative Medicine. *Archives of Internal Medicine*. 2001;161(19):2288-2292. doi:10.1001/archinte.161.19.2288
20. *Charell v. Gonzalez*, 251 A.D.2d 72 | Casetext Search + Citor. Accessed November 3, 2023. <https://casetext.com/case/charell-v-gonzalez-1>
21. Studdert DM. Legal issues in the delivery of alternative medicine. *J Am Med Womens Assoc* (1972). 1999;54(4):173-176.
22. *May a patient consent to unorthodox treatment? - Schneider v. Revici*, 817 F.2d 987 (2nd Cir. 1987). Accessed November 3, 2023. <https://biotech.law.lsu.edu/cases/consent/Revici.htm>
23. Gilmour J, Harrison C, Asadi L, Cohen MH, Vohra S. Informed consent: advising patients and parents about complementary and alternative medicine therapies. *Pediatrics*. 2011;128 Suppl 4:S187-192. doi:10.1542/peds.2010-2720H
24. Rudra S, Kalra A, Kumar A, Joe W. Utilization of alternative systems of medicine as health care services in India: Evidence on AYUSH care from NSS 2014. *PLoS One*. 2017;12(5):e0176916. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0176916

Leveraging Healthcare Policy for Climate Action: Medicaid's Underutilized Potential

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Abstract

Climate change is a local, national, and global public health crisis. Increased extreme weather variations, heat waves, climate-related displacement, morbidity due to pollution, mental health conditions, and infectious disease transmission are mere examples of current and future impacts on population health. State Medicaid agencies have a unique opportunity to catalyze change in health policy that can address local and national needs for climate action. Medicaid Section 1115 demonstration waivers, for example, may be used to fund innovative projects to support those affected by extreme weather conditions. Expanding telehealth coverage may provide continuity of care for patients unable to access in-person services, while reducing greenhouse gas emissions on physical clinical space and transportation. State Medicaid agencies may financially incentivize the monitoring and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions by individual healthcare facilities, further encouraging transparent quality improvement metrics to identify future innovations on a local scale. Leveraging Medicaid's health policy reach to support climate action addresses the healthcare sector's responsibility to reduce contributions to climate change while creating initiatives that support population health for those acutely affected. In recognizing the disproportionate burden that climate change places on the health of marginalized groups, these health policy actions are prudent and necessary.

Introduction

Population Health & Climate Change

Climate change is one of the most pressing population health crises of our time. In North America, more than 191,000 deaths per year are related to extreme weather variations. [1,2]In 2021, a one-week heat wave caused 600 deaths in Washington and Oregon alone.[3] Worsening air pollution from wildfires has been linked to greater acute hospital admissions for cardiovascular and respiratory disease.[4] Exposure to wildfires during pregnancy is associated with worse birth outcomes.[5] In 2020, greater air particulate matter from wildfires was found to increase COVID-19-related deaths across the western United States.[6] Vector-borne disease spread is also amplified. A recent systematic review found that transmission of 218 out of 375 infectious diseases affecting humans are directly affected by climate change.[7] Global warming, precipitation changes, and environmental habitat expansions are associated with increased outbreaks of Zika[8], malaria[8], dengue[8], trypanosomiasis, and plague.[11,9]

Evidence of climate change's effects on mental health are apparent. Individuals with direct experiences with flooding are more likely to experience depression and anxiety.[10] Children exposed to natural disasters are more likely to have long-term mental health consequences.[11–13] [77]For both acute and long-term health outcomes, the need to address climate change is clear.

The Role of Health Policy

US healthcare is a major contributor to environmental damage. A 2020 analysis showed that greenhouse gas emissions from US health care reached 1,692 kg per capita in 2018, contributing to the loss of 388,000 disability-adjusted-life-years in one year alone.[14] Sources of the sector's greenhouse gas emissions include healthcare facilities, such as on-site boilers and maintenance electricity, and supply-chain emissions from production, transportation, and storage of medical equipment.[14] The healthcare sector is responsible for 8.5% of the nation's greenhouse gas emissions.[14] Globally, US healthcare is responsible for one-quarter of all global healthcare-related greenhouse gas emission.[15] US healthcare policy has a responsibility to leverage its resources to catalyze change for environmental health.

The United States, like other countries, has begun to make policy changes that address this opportunity. In 2022, the Biden Administration announced the Health Sector Climate Pledge – a plan to halve healthcare-related greenhouse gas emissions by 2050.[16] 61 healthcare entities, including both public and private hospital organizations, the Department of Veterans (VA), medical device suppliers, and over 200 federal hospitals and facilities from the DHHS pledged their commitment.[16]

Section 1115 Demonstrations

The large purchasing power of Medicaid in healthcare facilities, as well as its state-wide regulatory capacity, can catalyze greater change.[17]For example, state Medicaid agencies can receive multi-year funding for innovative projects through Department of Health and Human Services Section 1115 Demonstration waivers. State agencies may submit a proposal aimed to support their local beneficiaries in a topic of interest for the state. In this way, Medicaid agencies may use Section 1115 funding to build innovative projects that support both Medicaid beneficiaries and climate action.[18]

Oregon's Section 1115 Demonstration waiver provides housing, climate, and nutrition support for those who face extreme weather events across the state.[19] In this program, Oregon Health Plan (OHP) members can receive extra air conditioners, air filters, backup power sources to operate medical devices (i.e. ventilators), and mini refrigerators to store medications, during climate-related emergencies.[19] Many medications – including antibiotics and insulin – may not be safe to use without proper refrigeration, making this initiative essential in mitigating climate disaster-related impacts on routine health maintenance.

In addition to reducing disruptions to medication adherence, preventing acute heat stroke, and reducing pollution-related respiratory conditions, this innovative program has the potential to address

climate action through an equitable lens. OHP members who were released from incarceration in the last 12 months, are currently or previously involved with the state's child welfare system, or are unhoused, automatically qualify for these devices.[19] In this way, Oregon's innovative program addresses the links between population health equity and climate change. Climate emergencies are known to exacerbate racial disparities in health outcomes. Climate-change events, such as heatwaves, floods, and wildfires, disproportionately affect Black, Latinx, Native American, Pacific Islander, and Asian communities.[20] Oregon's use of the Section 1115 Medicaid waiver both supports healthcare facilities in times of climate-related emergency while supporting the population health through a lens of public health justice.

Expanding Telehealth

Outside of Section 1115 waivers, State Medicaid agencies can be catalysts for climate action by supporting telehealth and encouraging transparent sustainability data in healthcare delivery.[21] The COVID-19 pandemic allowed certain healthcare services to be delivered virtually, as many state Medicaid agencies began to cover telehealth for beneficiaries.[21] In North Carolina, for example, pandemic-related legislature allowed Medicaid reimbursement for telehealth psychiatric diagnostic appointments and psychotherapy.[22] Although not all medical appointments are appropriately suited for virtual visits, expanding the use of telehealth can provide greater continuity of care and may reduce greenhouse gas emissions from transportation and office use for patients and providers alike.[21] A recent systematic review found that travel-associated greenhouse gas emission savings 'significantly outweighed the carbon footprint of telehealth equipment', estimating that telehealth visits reduced carbon dioxide emissions by 0.70 to 372 kg per visit.[23]

Monitoring Quality Improvement

To monitor their progress on healthcare-related greenhouse gas emissions, state Medicaid agencies can leverage financial incentives for quality improvement metrics. In Washington State, the Medicaid Quality Incentive provides healthcare facilities with a percent-financial incentive for completing a survey on their direct and indirect greenhouse gas emissions.[24,25] Participating hospitals are then asked to collaborate with teams on goals to address improvements.[25] In this way, the state Medicaid agency is able to collect facility-level information on climate action progress to guide future policies. At a national level, opportunities for increasing quality improvement metrics are vast. The Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services Decarbonization and Resilience Initiative will invite acute care hospitals to report data on organizational, building energy, anesthetic gas, and transportation emissions from 2026 until 2030.[26] Hospitals may then opt-in to receive individualized feedback, compare progress with other facilities, and have the ability to receive national recognition for their improvements.[26]

Conclusion

State Medicaid agencies face a unique opportunity to support the public health of their beneficiaries by leveraging healthcare policy to address climate action. Through Section 1115 waivers, innovative projects, and transparent quality improvement monitoring, Medicaid can use its vast resources to address healthcare's burden on climate change. In doing so, policies can equitably improve environmental and population health alike.

References

1. Zhao Q, Guo Y, Ye T, et al. Global, regional, and national burden of mortality associated with non-optimal ambient temperatures from 2000 to 2019: a three-stage modelling study. *Lancet Planet Health*. 2021;5(7):e415-e425. doi:10.1016/S2542-5196(21)00081-4
2. IDMC Grid 2016 - Global Report on Internal Displacement. Accessed June 11, 2024. <https://www.internal-displacement.org/globalreport2016/>
3. Hidden Toll of the Northwest Heat Wave: Hundreds of Extra Deaths - The New York Times. Accessed June 11, 2024. <https://www.nytimes.com/interactive/2021/08/11/climate/deaths-pacific-northwest-heat-wave.html>
4. Borchers Arriagada N, Palmer AJ, Bowman DM, Morgan GG, Jalaludin BB, Johnston FH. Unprecedented smoke-related health burden associated with the 2019–20 bushfires in eastern Australia. *Medical Journal of Australia*. 2020;213(6):282-283. doi:10.5694/mja2.50545
5. Heft-Neal S, Driscoll A, Yang W, Shaw G, Burke M. Associations between wildfire smoke exposure during pregnancy and risk of preterm birth in California. *Environ Res*. 2022;203:111872. doi:10.1016/j.envres.2021.111872
6. Zhou X, Josey K, Kamareddine L, et al. Excess of COVID-19 cases and deaths due to fine particulate matter exposure during the 2020 wildfires in the United States. *Sci Adv*. 2021;7(33). doi:10.1126/sciadv.abi8789
7. Mora C, McKenzie T, Gaw IM, et al. Over half of known human pathogenic diseases can be aggravated by climate change. *Nat Clim Chang*. 2022;12(9):869-875. doi:10.1038/s41558-022-01426-1
8. Nava A, Shimabukuro JS, Chmura AA, Luz SLB. The Impact of Global Environmental Changes on Infectious Disease Emergence with a Focus on Risks for Brazil. *ILAR J*. 2017;58(3):393-400. doi:10.1093/ilar/ilx034
9. Gale P, Drew T, Phipps LP, David G, Wooldridge M. The effect of climate change on the occurrence and prevalence of livestock diseases in Great Britain: a review. *J Appl Microbiol*. 2009;106(5):1409-1423. doi:10.1111/j.1365-2672.2008.04036.x
10. French CE, Waite TD, Armstrong B, Rubin GJ, Beck CR, Oliver I. Impact of repeat flooding on mental health and health-related quality of life: a cross-sectional analysis of the English National Study of Flooding and Health. *BMJ Open*. 2019;9(11):e031562. doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2019-031562
11. Catani C, Gewirtz AH, Wieling E, Schauer E, Elbert T, Neuner F. Tsunami, War, and Cumulative Risk in the Lives of Sri Lankan Schoolchildren. *Child Dev*. 2010;81(4):1176-1191. doi:10.1111/j.1467-8624.2010.01461.x
12. Mohammad L, Peek L. Exposure Outliers: Children, Mothers, and Cumulative Disaster Exposure in Louisiana. *J Family Strengths*. 2019;19(1). doi:10.58464/2168-670X.1401
13. Garfin DR, Silver RC, Gil-Rivas V, et al. Children's reactions to the 2010 Chilean earthquake: The role of trauma exposure, family context, and school-based mental health programming. *Psychol Trauma*. 2014;6(5):563-573. doi:10.1037/a0036584
14. Eckelman MJ, Huang K, Lagasse R, Senay E, Dubrow R, Sherman JD. Health Care Pollution And Public Health Damage In The United States: An Update. *Health Aff*. 2020;39(12):2071-2079. doi:10.1377/hlthaff.2020.01247
15. Dzau VJ, Levine R, Barrett G, Witty A. Decarbonizing the U.S. Health Sector — A Call to Action. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2021;385(23):2117-2119. doi:10.1056/NEJMp2115675
16. Health Sector Leaders Join Biden Administration's Pledge to Reduce Greenhouse Gas Emissions 50% by 2030.; 2022.
17. Shattuck P, Haley C, Cross E. The Untapped Potential of Medicaid to Reduce Greenhouse Gas Emissions. The Commonwealth Fund .
18. Foundation KF. Medicaid Waiver Tracker: Approved and Pending Section 1115 Waivers by State. The Henry J Kaiser Family Foundation. Published online 2019.
19. Oregon Health Plan (OHP) Climate Supports. Oregon Health Authority.
20. Berberian AG, Gonzalez DJX, Cushing LJ. Racial Disparities in Climate Change-Related Health Effects in the United States. *Curr Environ Health Rep*. 2022;9(3):451-464. doi:10.1007/s40572-022-00360-w
21. Harrison E, Haley C, Shattuck C. Medicaid Policy Options: Innovative Approaches to Support the Reduction of Harmful Greenhouse Gas Emissions from the Health System.; 2023.
22. Kuhn J, Thompson S, Fletcher H, Koenigsmark T, Dowler S. NC Medicaid's Telehealth Evolution: Access and Utilization in a Post-Pandemic State. *N C Med J*. 2024;85(2). doi:10.18043/001c.94867
23. Purohit A, Smith J, Hibble A. Does telemedicine reduce the carbon footprint of healthcare? A systematic review. *Future Healthc J*. 2021;8(1):e85-e91. doi:10.7861/fhj.2020-0080
24. Medicaid Quality Incentive. Washington State Hospital Administration.

25. Ovchyan M. Climate Change: Monitoring of Greenhouse Gas Emissions . Washington State Hospital Administration .
26. Fact Sheet: TEAM Decarbonization and Resilience Initiative. Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services.